

Evolution of Open Access Policies and Availability, 1996–2013

RTD-B6-PP-2011-2: Study to develop a set of indicators to measure open access

Prepared by

Science-Metrix

info@science-metrix.com
www.science-metrix.com

Produced and written by

Éric Archambault, Didier Amyot, David Campbell, Julie Caruso, Philippe Deschamps, Aurore Nicol, Françoise Provencher, Lise Rebout & Guillaume Roberge

D 4.5 version: 5p
Date: 20/10/2014

This document forms a part of a series of reports produced as part of the European Commission Contract RTD-B6-PP-2011-2—Study to develop a set of indicators to measure open access:

- Archambault, E. et al. (2014). *Proportion of Open Access Papers Published in Peer-Reviewed Journals at the European and World Levels—1996–2013*. Deliverable D.1.8. (2014 Update). Version 11b.
- Archambault, E. Caruso, J., & Nicol, A, (2014) *State-of-art analysis of OA strategies to peer-review publications*. Deliverable D.2.1. (2014 Update). Version 5b.
- Caruso, J., Nicol, A, & Archambault, E. (2014) *State-of-art analysis of OA strategies to scientific data*. Deliverable D.2.2. (2014 Update). Version 4b.
- Caruso, J., Nicol, A, & Archambault, E. (2014) *Comparative analysis of the strengths and weaknesses of existing open access strategies*. Deliverable D.2.3. (2014 Update). Version 4b.
- Campbell, D., Nicol, A, & Archambault, E. (2014) *Composite indicator to measure the growth of Open Access*. Deliverable D.3.2. Version 1.
- Archambault, E. et al. (2014). *Evolution of Open Access Policies and Availability, 1996–2013*. Deliverable D.4.5. Version 5b.

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Executive Summary

The ineffectual situation whereby publicly-funded research results published in peer reviewed journals continue to sit behind a ‘pay wall’, a situation made worse by continuous increases in the price of scholarly journal subscriptions, has fuelled the popularity of open access (OA) in recent years. In response to what many perceive to be a dysfunctional system, individual researchers, libraries, universities, research funders, and governments have become incentivised to join the campaign for OA. Borne on the back of the digital revolution, the movement towards OA to scholarly knowledge is transforming the global research communication and dissemination system.

This report presents a summary of this series of studies. It examines the current state of the art of OA strategies to peer-review publications (Part I), a state-of-the-art analysis of OA strategies to scientific data (Part II). A third part of the study performs an assessment of the proportion and the number of OA papers published in peer-reviewed scientific journals. The last part compares the results of policies and strategies across countries and explores policy implications. The study focuses on the 28 member states of the European Union (EU28), as well as the European Research Area (ERA), Brazil, Canada, Japan, and the US.

I—Analysis of OA strategies to peer-reviewed publications

This section examines the policies and strategies of the main institutional actors in the OA movement—governments, funding bodies, and research institutions—and describes the response of scientific journal publishers.

Governmental OA strategies

Most national governments have not proposed or implemented direct legislation on OA. Instead, OA is often addressed through less formal means, such as the production of guidelines for research funding agencies. Related legislation often includes laws on copyright and licensing; in fact, the vast majority of countries covered in this study have copyright legislation that may apply to peer-reviewed publications. Legislation directly addressing OA has been implemented in the US, Spain, and Germany. Italy and Lithuania have also recently passed laws that have direct implications for OA in those countries.

- In the US, the Consolidated Appropriations Act, 2008, is the legislative basis for the OA policy of the National Institutes of Health (NIH). With this legislation, the US became the first country to adopt a national OA mandate. The Fair Access to Science and Technology Research Act (FASTR) was introduced in Congress in February 2013. At the same time, the White House’s Office of Science and Technology Policy (OSTP) issued a Directive on Public Access. Both require all federal agencies with extramural research expenditures of over \$100 million to develop a federal research public access policy. On January 17, 2014, an omnibus federal spending bill, similar in concept to the OSTP Directive, was signed into law by President Obama; it includes an OA mandate (Section 527 of the Consolidated Appropriations Act, 2014 [H.R.3547]).
- Spain passed the national Law on Science, Technology and Innovation (2011) (Ley de la Ciencia). Article 37 mandates that a digital version of the final copy of research accepted for publication and funded under the national public R&D funding scheme be deposited in an OA repository within 12 months of publication.
- In Germany, legislation (BGB1. I S. 3714) enacted on October 1, 2013, allows authors to make any of their articles stemming from publicly-funded research openly accessible and available for non-commercial purposes without the consent of the publishers 12 months after first publication.
- Italy’s Law of 7 October 2013 (No. 112) includes a regulation for OA to scientific publications. Researchers whose research has been publicly funded (at least 50%) are required to either publish their work in an OA journal or deposit their work in OA archives within 18 to 24 months after publication.

A number of countries in the ERA have instituted national policies, programmes, and principles related to OA.

- The UK is a leader in the development of OA, with the Higher Education Funding Council for England (HEFCE) and the Research Councils UK (RCUK) pushing for greater public access to publicly-supported research, and the 2012 ‘Finch Report’ raising awareness of and fostering discussion on OA in the country. Jisc, a UK registered charity that champions the use of digital technologies in UK education and research, has also had a considerable influence. The 2013 Policy on Open Access, drafted by the Working Group on Expanding Access to Published Research Findings, chaired by Dame Janet Finch, will make all government-funded research OA within five years.
- In Ireland, the National Principles for Open Access Policy Statement (2012) mandates the deposit of outputs of funded research in OA repositories.
- Since 2006, Sweden has had a national OA programme, OpenAccess.se, which has played a role in the creation of a national search portal for scholarly publications (SwePub), the Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ), and a number of institutional and funder policies.
- France’s HAL multi-disciplinary open archive was launched by the Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique (CNRS) in 2001.

At the pan-European level, the Open Access Pilot was launched by the European Commission as part of its Seventh Framework Programme (FP7) in August 2008. Within several thematic areas of the framework programme, FP7 projects are required to deposit peer-reviewed research articles or final manuscripts resulting from projects into an online repository. Other Europe-wide initiatives include the Digital Repository Infrastructure Vision for European Research (DRIVER), established to build a cohesive network of repositories for research and education, and the Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe (OpenAIRE), a complementary project offering organisational and technological infrastructure for the identification, deposition, access and monitoring of FP7 and European Research Council (ERC) funded publications. Launched in February 2014, a new 30-month project titled PASTEUR4OA (Open Access Policy Alignment Strategies for European Union Research) aims to help Member States to develop and/or reinforce OA strategies and policies at the national level and facilitate coordination among Member States.

At the international level, research-performing organisations also contribute to the global spread of OA. Since 2010, much of the World Bank’s research has been made available to the public through its website and the Open Data Initiative and Access to Information Policy. Furthermore, its new OA policy, effective since July 1, 2012, adopts the Creative Commons Attribution (CC-BY) copyright licence for all of its outputs and other knowledge products, solidifying the World Bank’s position as a forerunner in OA.

Funding bodies’ policies and mandates

An analysis of funding bodies’ OA policies was performed to assess the extensiveness of OA policies and to examine OA rules for grant recipients, across ERA countries and in Brazil, Canada, Japan, and the US. The country with the highest number of OA policies is the UK (with 34 mandates), followed by Canada (14), the US (9), Denmark (6), Ireland (5), and France (5). Importantly though, the number of policies alone is a weak indicator of commitment to OA in a given country.

An analysis of 48 implemented funder policies in the countries was conducted, and startling differences were found in the level of detail provided. Funding agencies that are building a new OA policy or renewing a pre-existing policy should consider a number of key points for transparency. These include the following:

- Coverage of article processing charges (APCs): 46% of funders indicated that they would cover the APCs, and 12% indicated that they would not. The remaining 42% of policies did not specify whether funders would pay the fees.

- Preference for Green or Gold OA: Except for the UK which favoured Gold OA, most favoured Green (40%), while 2% mandated both Green OA and Gold OA, and 58% expressed no preference. If Green OA is allowed, specific repositories may be identified.
- Acceptable types of documents and metadata: 80% of policies specified that articles should be deposited in their final accepted version or post-print.
- Funding share scope: Guidelines must clarify at what point the policy applies with respect to a certain percentage of funding provided or the number of authors who are grantees.
- Embargoes: If the policy supports Green OA, embargoes are frequently accepted to give publishers exclusivity for a limited time. Though this diverges from the ideal form of OA, which stipulates that results be available immediately, among the 48 funder policies reviewed, 77% accepted embargoes between 6 and 12 months.
- Though compliance with policy is currently seldom tracked or reported, clear rules should be mentioned.
- Other items that may be listed in the policy include the prescribed timing of deposits, exceptions in types of outputs, the transfer of rights, and sanctions.

Research institutions' OA strategies

The ERA countries, Brazil, Canada, Japan, and the US collectively have 293 institutional, multi-institutional, sub-institutional, and thesis OA mandates presently in place in addition to 70 proposed institutional, multi-institutional, and sub-institutional OA mandates and non-mandates. The largest number of mandates is in the US, the UK, Italy, Finland, and Portugal.

A survey of head librarians at universities and higher-learning institutions was conducted for this study. The survey found that 73% of respondents agreed or strongly agreed with the statement 'Providing open access to scholarly publications is a priority in [their] organisation'. A similar proportion agreed or strongly agreed with the statement 'Providing open access to scholarly publications is a priority in [their] country'. However, only 42% of these respondents stated that their organisation has an OA policy on scholarly publications. Among these respondents, 22% declared that their organisation's policy is not publicly available.

Within the ERA, Brazil, Canada, Japan, and the US, nearly 40 million records were spread across 1,450 institutional repositories in April 2014, as reported in OpenDOAR alone. Institutional repositories account for 28% of records in OA repositories (disciplinary repositories account for 38%, governmental repositories for 25%, and aggregating repositories for 9%) (as of April 2013). Importantly, these records are highly heterogeneous. OA institutional repositories contain digital images, music, and text. Only a portion of the text files is made up of peer-reviewed scholarly papers. Hence, the presence of records in repositories is not a robust proxy for the availability of scientific papers and won't be so until repositories are characterised with all due care.

Repository development presents numerous challenges related to intellectual property rights, data curation, long-term preservation, infrastructure development and interoperability. The greatest strength of many repositories is the large number of records they contain, not necessarily the quality and value of their data. Records are composed solely of incomplete metadata and, frequently, contain no link to articles or other digital objects.

Universities also struggle with promoting OA within the academic community. Incentives are essential for reaching researchers who are reticent about OA or who are deterred by the trade-off between the costs and benefits of making their work OA. Survey results suggest that direct advantages for researchers who make their work available in OA form remain rare at the level of institutions. Of survey respondents, 49% indicated that researchers in their organisation were encouraged to archive their scholarly work but without any formal reward, and 36% indicated that their institution had no policy in this regard. Meanwhile, only 15% of respondents indicated that self-archiving was mandatory, and 14% stated that financial support was available for researchers who published in OA journals.

Effects on and response of scientific journal publishers

In response to the changing landscape of scholarly communication, publishers have developed new products known as 'big deals'. Contracts are established between libraries and publishers whereby libraries secure access to a large set of journals distributed by the publisher, mostly in electronic format, for a set price, for a period of three to five years, and for all faculty and students at the subscribing university. Though this has had the effect of theoretically lowering the subscription cost per journal, the negotiating power of research libraries has fallen, and they do not necessarily end up with an optimal mix of journals. Another effect of this strategy is to augment the market presence of large publishers, who can impose journals of lesser interest to researchers due to their being packaged with their 'must subscribe to' journals.

Mergers and acquisitions in the scholarly communication sector have increased the concentration of journals in the hands of a limited number of publishers. As a result, librarians have little power to opt out of big deals or negotiate the terms of subscriptions contracts. As the price of serials, particularly the highly sought after ones, has continued to rise faster than inflation, library budgets have increased moderately, stagnated or even decreased, a situation referred to as the 'serials crisis'.

There is tension between universities and publishers, which are suspected of 'double dipping', that is, charging article processing charges while subsequently obtaining revenue from journal subscriptions. In response to rising complaints, many publishers provide publication charge discounts to authors from institutions that subscribe to a relevant "Hybrid" journal (a paid access journal comprising a number of Gold OA articles). Other journals offer discounts to society members or institutions that have purchased institutional memberships.

Although it is commonly assumed that there are many vested interests in preserving the status quo of the current subscription market, many publishers have recognised that OA can lead to wider dissemination, maximised market reach, greater visibility and higher journal citation impact factors for their articles. Yet, OA journals have been confronted with the challenge of adopting a funding model that is consistent with their survival. Several models for OA publishing that differ with respect to type of content access, retention of author's rights and type of financing have emerged. These models include OA journals that are free for authors and readers; OA journals that are free for authors and readers of the online version, with subscription payment for the paper version; 'author pays' OA journals; hybrid systems; journals with free access to certain content; and journals with free access to contents after an embargo period.

In recent years, many traditional commercial publishers—including the Nature Publishing Group, Springer, and Elsevier—have established sizable OA journal operations or have extended their Hybrid OA operations. Successful 'Mega-OA' journals have also been established, most notably PLoS ONE (Public Library of Science) and Scientific Reports (Nature Publishing Group), and these have had a positive impact on the credibility of OA.

Journal publishers are also increasingly allowing article archiving. As compiled in SHERPA/RoMEO, from January 2004 to April 2014, the number of publishers' OA policies allowing some form of archiving grew steadily, from 80 to close to 1,700. Of these, 31% allow post-print archiving, 33% allow pre-print and post-print archiving, and 9% allow pre-print archiving only. The remaining 27% of publishers do not formally allow any form of archiving but may agree to special arrangements with authors, particularly in the context of a funder mandate.

II—Analysis of OA strategies to scientific data

This part of the study examines strategies to foster open access to scientific data—such as incentives given at the researcher and institutional levels—and examines how, and whether, these policies are monitored and enforced. The infrastructure developed to store and share OA scientific data is also examined.

Governmental OA scientific data strategies

The political and administrative agendas in a rising number of countries now include the definition of open data strategies for public research through a range of projects, declarations, and policies, including legislation. To date, most national open data policies target datasets for government data that are not necessarily generated through scientific research but may be used for research, rather than scientific data at large. The countries with some of the largest numbers of open data strategies and open datasets are the United Kingdom (UK), the US, Denmark, Norway, the Netherlands, and Sweden.

The importance of comprehensive OA policies was recognised in 2004 by the Ministers of Science and Technology of the then 30 OECD countries, and of China, Israel, Russia, and South Africa. Governments may reap important economic benefits from the release of OA scientific data, such as through innovation-driven economic growth and job creation and more informed policy and research.

It has been estimated that, by unlocking the potential of big data, developed European economies could save between €150 billion and €300 billion annually in the form of operational efficiency gains and increased potential versus actual collection of tax revenue alone. A study has estimated the value of direct and indirect economic impacts of government-owned data across the EU-27 at €140 billion annually. It also estimated that, with lower barriers and improved infrastructure, this value could have been around €200 billion in 2008, representing 1.7% of the European GDP for that year.

In order to unlock the full economic potential of OA scientific data, machines must be able to access and mine this information without copyright infringement. The European Commission's Working Group on Text and Data Mining (TDM) Licences for Europe initiative has addressed this challenge through stakeholder dialogue. However, representatives from groups of researchers, science organisations, libraries, and small and medium enterprises have withdrawn from the process, arguing that the Working Group's decision to place licensing at the centre of discussions constitutes a bias against other solutions to adapt the legal framework to TDM applications.

The EU issued a directive on the reuse of public sector information as early as 2003, while the US government was the first to establish its own open data portal, data.gov, in 2009. National public data repositories were launched in 20 countries in the following years.

Major international organisations, including the United Nations, OECD, European Commission, International Energy Agency (IEA), Nuclear Energy Agency (NEA), Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA), and International Transport Forum (ITF), have also established open data portals. The World Bank's repository, data.worldbank.org, launched in 2011, is a landmark repository in terms of its usability by machines and humans alike.

States, provinces, and municipalities own the bulk of currently available open governmental data repositories. Notable governments and funding bodies that have initiated OA scientific databases include the NIH's GenBank, the DNA DataBank of Japan (DDBJ), the European Molecular Biology Laboratory (EMBL) Nucleotide Sequence Database, and the ClinicalTrials.gov database.

Funding bodies' strategies

Funding bodies may have an interest in archiving and disseminating data generated by their grantees to monitor the outcomes of their investments, increase the visibility of their

contribution to research, and ensure long-term preservation of the data. Mining and further analysing the data collected from multiple projects could also highlight underrepresented or emerging areas of interest.

Funding bodies have far fewer OA policies for scientific data than policies for scientific publications. In an analysis conducted by Science-Metrix of 48 funders' OA policies listed in ROARMAP within ERA countries, Brazil, Canada, and the US, 23% explicitly excluded data from OA requirements, and 38% did not mention data at all. Conversely, 29% of policies mandated open data archiving and 10% encouraged it without mandating it.

Although they are still in the minority, funding agencies that expect applicants to create and adhere to data storage, access, and management plans are increasing in number, with many agencies attaching conditions that strongly encourage or require the sharing of data with as few restrictions as possible and within a specified time frame.

Research institutions' strategies

OA policies for scientific data are less common than OA policies for scholarly publications. Yet, OA scientific data has the potential to strengthen the credibility of scholarly publications and research institutions, as it opens peer-review to the entire scientific community. A growing trend has been reported in the percentage of published articles retracted for fraud or suspected fraud. Easily accessible data could extend the peer-review process beyond a small group of reviewers acting before publication, to all readers after publication.

Few institutional repositories are dedicated exclusively to research data. Institutional repositories generally support datasets on repositories devoted to books, theses, peer-reviewed publications, and multimedia objects. Moreover, the infrastructure required to host and share scientific data, while still uncommon, is more developed than the associated policy frameworks. In the survey, 36% of respondents indicated that their organisation maintains one or more repositories for OA scientific data, whereas only 11% indicated that their organisation had a policy to this effect.

The survey's results also suggest that a significant number of existing OA repositories for scientific data are not indexed in ROAR and OpenDOAR, the directories used in this study. This impression is reinforced by the absence of known open data repositories, such as the NASA's AERONET and the European Molecular Biology Laboratory's databases. The repositories listed could merely be the tip of the iceberg.

III—Analysis of the proportion and number of papers available in OA

This core part of the study assessed the free availability of scholarly publications during the 1996 to 2013 period. It is the largest scale measurement of open access availability performed to date: a sample of one-quarter of a million records was used to study the historical evolution of OA between 1996 and 2013 and a larger, one-million-record sample, was used to perform an in-depth assessment of the proportion and scientific impact of OA between 2008 and 2013 in different types of OA, for different scientific fields of knowledge, and for 44 countries comprising the EU28 and ERA countries and the world.

Compared to previous studies done on the availability of OA, the present study presents the following characteristics: (1) it used the Scopus database, which currently covers a broader range of journals from various countries and scientific disciplines than other comprehensive databases; (2) it uses a simple definition of OA—freely available online to all (no money had to be paid, no registration to a service or website had to be made); (3) it used huge samples to maximise statistical precision; (4) it made careful and extensive efforts to harvest papers wherever they could be downloaded for free without restriction, rather than using a single existing search engine in order to obtain a high 'recall' rate (that is, the capacity to retrieve a large part of the relevant records), while, in addition, carefully minimising the number of false records collected (that is, the approach maximised retrieval precision); and (5) it carefully characterised the strengths and weaknesses of the measurement instrument in order to apply a correction that would provide a truer measure based on an Adjusted OA score.

This study also provided a series of rational definitions of access, open access, and ideal open access (see above). The definitions include aspects such as restrictions, payment, delay, transiency, and legitimacy. Because of the limited means (time and budget) available for this project, it was necessary to use operational definitions of OA that do not provide all the details one may wish to obtain. Though it was easy to obtain a clear and operational definition of Gold OA by stating that it referred to papers published in Gold OA journals listed in the DOAJ, defining and measuring Green OA was more challenging. The operational definition restricted Green OA to researchers' self-archived papers in institutional and some thematic repositories listed in OpenDOAR and ROAR. This left a sizeable residual number of papers that could still be downloaded for free; these were classified as Other OA. This comprises, for example, Gold OA papers from subscription-based journals, which are made available through article processing charges (APC). Other OA also include papers available in large repositories such as PubMed Central and on aggregator sites such as CiteSeerX. There are also Robin Hood OA or Rogue OA papers, that is, papers that infringe on copyrights by making them accessible to the public despite licenses that restrict them to being behind pay walls.

Measurement instrument calibration

A sample of 500 articles from a pilot study (December 2012) and a previous version of this study (April 2013) was used to characterise the harvester employed to measure the proportion of OA papers. Slight variations were observed in the availability of articles in this sample measured in December 2012 (47.6%), April 2013 (44.8%) and April 2014 (48.6%). It is noteworthy that 272 articles, that is, about 54.4%, were available for free at one time or another between December 2012 and April 2013. These results suggest that important transient aspects need to be taken into consideration while measuring OA availability. These results also show that the harvesting engine developed by Science-Metrix has very good retrieval precision (99.1%) and fairly good recall (86.4%), resulting in fairly robust measures of OA availability. This characterisation of the measurement instrument made it possible to calibrate to produce 'Adjusted OA' measures. The total OA measures by the harvester are multiplied by 1.146. However, because the sample size of the calibration was only 500 records, the margin of error of the calibration is a fairly large ± 4.5 percentage points.

Evolution of the proportion and the number of OA papers

As of April 2014, more than 50% of the scientific papers published in 2007, 2008, 2009, 2010, 2011, and 2012 can be downloaded for free on the Internet. Only one year ago, in April 2013, the proportion of papers that was freely available was just a hair below 50% (49.54%) in 2011 and did not reach that mark for any other year. On average, the citation advantage of OA papers is 40%, while the citation disadvantage is 27% for non-OA papers (based on a total sample size of 209,000 papers).

The growth of OA appears as the result of four main forces: (1) historical growth in the interest in OA, which translates into *new papers* being increasingly available for free; (2) the growing interest in OA translates into actors increasingly making *old papers* available for free; (3) OA policies that allow for delaying OA produce a concomitant disembargoing of scientific articles, which creates additional growth in old papers being made available for free; and (4) the number of published scientific papers is growing, so even for a stable proportion of OA, the number of OA papers would keep growing.

The effect of backfilling has not been studied extensively before. Evidence suggests that during the last year alone, some 700,000 papers indexed in Scopus between 1996 and 2011 became available for free, that is, an extra 3.9 percentage points. Studying the OA availability curve for the 2004–2011 period of one year ago compared to this year (April 2013 vs. April 2014) reveals that the present curve has made an upward translation of 3.6 percentage points (measured for 2004); in addition to going up, the curve is also becoming steeper—the exponent of the curve increased from 1.9% overall growth to 2.4% growth this year. This means backfilling is accelerating over time.

The statistics just presented were on the proportion of OA; it is also relevant to assess how the number of papers is growing per se. These data show that, as of April 2014, the number of available papers increased by 9.4% per year. Of the papers published in 1996, 240,000 are now available for free, as are 950,000 of the papers published in 2012. Based on the Adjusted OA availability statistics, one can estimate that about 47% of the papers indexed in Scopus between 1996 and 2013 can be downloaded for free as of April 2014. This means that 10.1 million papers of the 21.5 million papers indexed in Scopus for that period are downloadable.

While the number of Green OA papers has grown steadily, this appears to be due to background growth, that is, the growth in published scientific papers. Green OA as a percentage of the papers indexed in Scopus appears to have levelled off from around 2004. This requires further investigation to determine whether this is measurement artefact—an effect of the imperfect operational definition of Green OA used here—or whether Green OA is somewhat losing steam. Despite this, there were approximately 1.2 million papers available in Green OA form in repositories across the world, and the growth rate of OA papers was 8.8% between 1997 and 2011.

The percentage of peer-reviewed articles published in Gold OA journals indexed in Scopus for 1996 was only 0.9%, but grew to 12.8% for 2012, the annual growth rate being 18% for this period, which means that the proportion of articles in Gold OA journals doubles every 4.1 years. Scopus covers less than half of the quantity of journals listed in the DOAJ, so this figure likely underestimates the true extent of the role played by Gold OA journals.

Gold OA papers indexed in Scopus grew exponentially up until 2012. The growth rate was 24% per year between 1996 and 2012, which means that the number of papers published in Gold OA journals doubles every 3.2 years. There are currently about 1,380,000 papers from Gold journals indexed in Scopus for 1996 to 2013. This represents only 200,000 papers more than those available in Green OA form, but Gold OA journals papers are growing with a clear momentum, which is not so clearly the case with Green OA available in institutional repositories.

The evolution of Other OA is somewhat similar to that of Green OA. In terms of percentage, it increased substantially from 1996 until about 2003, at which time it levelled off until 2008, when there was an observed decline in the proportion of Other OA papers. It is not so easy to determine what creates this shape due to the heterogeneity of the underlying dataset. What seems to be obvious here is that unless we are witnessing a slowdown in OA development, embargoing and others forms of DOA (Delayed OA) are having a very tangible effect on scientific knowledge availability. This creates a situation whereby a substantial part of the material openly available is relatively old, and as some would say, outdated. As in the case of Green OA, the growth as measured in number of papers is greater than the growth of the proportion. There was a regular increase of 8.4% per year in the number of papers from 1996 to 2009, after which the increase slowed down and dropped in 2013 as the full effect of embargoes surpassed the growth in available papers (which was 6.6% per year in Scopus between 2003 and 2012).

Green OA papers do not contribute a large share of the overall OA stock of papers. As seen previously, their number did not increase much after 2004. A word of warning here though: authors can also backfill repositories, and the current measurement does not take this into account as no baseline for Green OA was measured last year.

Other forms of OA—Gold OA Papers (that is, those with article processing charges published in subscription journal or so-called hybrid journals), Green DOA and Gold DOA (embargoed self-archiving and embargoed journals), ROA (Robin Hood or Rogue OA), and papers archived in non-institutional repositories such as ResearchGate—account for a large part of the pie. This large heterogeneous set contributes the largest proportion of OA papers, and there is therefore an urgent need to disaggregate this category. More research and more careful classification and thus finer-grained measures are required to better understand how these

various categories contribute to OA growth, what their pattern of time-delay is, what their transiency is (especially of the ROA), how important backfilling is and how far back it goes.

OA papers were between 26% and 64% more cited on average for any given year than all papers combined, whereas non-OA received between 17% and 33% fewer citations (based on a sample size of at least 10,000 papers any given year). Green OA and Other OA papers have somewhat similar patterns. Papers in subscription-based journals (non-OA articles only) and Gold OA journals are also somewhat similar to one another. On average, Green OA (operational definition used here) papers have the greatest citation advantage, being cited 53% more frequently than all papers. They are followed by the Other OA category, which is 47% more frequently cited on average. Papers published in Gold OA journals have a citation disadvantage of 35% on average, compared to a disadvantage of 27% for non-OA papers.

Evolution of OA by scientific field

Considering the last three years together (2011–2013), as of April 2014 more than 50% of the papers can be freely downloaded in 12 fields out of 22. A growth index was computed by dividing the percentage of OA availability in 2011 and 2012 by that observed in 2008 and 2009 (2013 was left aside as embargoes would distort calculated growth rates). Overall, between the two periods, there was a 4% increase in OA availability (slightly less than 2 percentage points). The fields with the fastest growth during these periods were general science & technology, enabling & strategic technologies, public health and health services, visual & performing arts, clinical medicine, and built & environment design. One can suspect that the NIH OA mandate is at play here (in public health and clinical medicine).

The absolute number of papers in OA form is rising rapidly (as there is also underlying growth in the number of papers generally). For example, the growth of the OA proportion in agriculture, fisheries & forestry was 1.02, but the number of papers grew at 1.16 (16% growth in the number of OA papers indexed in Scopus in 2011–2013 compared to the 2008–2009 period).

Overall, out of the 4.6 million scientific papers from peer-reviewed journals indexed in Scopus during the 2011–2013 period, 2.5 million were available for free in April 2014 (Adjusted OA score). A very large number of papers are freely available in clinical medicine (Adjusted OA = 680,000 papers), biomedical research, and physics and astronomy (close to 250,000 papers, as calculated with an adjusted measure). This is partly because of the policy of the NIH that mandates the use of the PubMed Central repository for supported research and because of the arXiv e-print archive, which has been largely adopted by researchers in the field of physics.

Scientific impact of OA and non-OA papers

All the fields derive an OA citation advantage. Paradoxically, many of the fields where the OA proportion is low have a sizeable citation advantage, such as the visual & performing arts (80% more cited), communication & textual studies (66%), philosophy & textual studies (63%), historical studies (55%), general arts, humanities and social sciences (51%), and engineering (38%). An explanation to this is likely to be that papers from researchers in these fields are more likely to have their papers used as there are fewer OA papers available.

There is a huge citation advantage to publishing in Green OA, as has been demonstrated time and again in other serious studies conducted previously. Papers in general science & technology, in historical studies and in visual & performing arts all receive, on average, twice as many citations as the overall population of papers. Two fields stand out for a fairly small Green OA citation advantage: clinical medicine (+8% vs. +56% in Other OA) and biomedical research (+10% vs. +23%). The reason may be that other sources of freely downloadable papers, classified here as 'Other OA', such as BioMed Central, are so large that the reflex of users is to first see what is available there and to shun institutional repositories. Still, 8% and 10% more citation remains a sizeable advantage, and it is worthwhile using institutional repositories and immediate Green OA to cut the delays associated with what many consider

to be weak OA mandates, that is, those allowing for papers to be embargoed instead of being made available immediately.

On average, publishing in Gold OA journals is the least advantageous solution if one wants to maximise scientific impact. It is still more advantageous than strict Paid Access in seven fields, and ranks as the second best solution for physics & astronomy. Currently, there is a marked disadvantage for publishing in Gold journals in general arts, humanities & social sciences, built environment & design, economics & business and visual & performing arts. Interestingly, visual & performing arts has one of the highest advantages derived from the use of Green OA and OA generally, yet it is the field with the least prevalent use of OA.

The statistics on Gold journals require careful interpretation. First, many Gold journals are younger and smaller, and these factors have an adverse effect on the citation rate and hence on measured citation scores. Authors frequently prefer reading and citing established journals, and it is therefore a challenge to start a journal from scratch, and to have authors submit high-quality articles. It takes time to build a reputation and to attract established authors.

OA in the ERA and four selected countries

An examination of OA availability was performed for EU28 and ERA countries and four additional countries, Brazil, Canada, Japan, and the US. For the 2008–2013 period considered as a whole, the Adjusted OA suggests that all 44 countries have more than 50% of papers in OA for that period. Four EU28 countries have even reached an aggregate availability score above 70%—the Netherlands, Croatia, Estonia, and Portugal. It is interesting to note that the Netherlands, which is also scientific publishers' land of predilection, is the EU country with the largest share of papers available in OA form (74%) as a whole for papers published in the 2008–2013 period and available for free download as of April 2014.

All ERA countries have tipped towards having a majority of papers in OA, though in the case of the Republic of Moldova, the margin of error is quite high, and it is quite possible that the country has not tipped to OA yet. Swiss researchers contribute to making their country a leader in OA, with 70% of the papers being downloadable for free.

In countries outside the ERA, it is noteworthy that the US has passed the tipping point by a fair margin (Adjusted OA = 67.9%), as is also the case for Canada (64.4%). Even more salient is the proportion of 76% observed in Brazil. This is no doubt due to the important contribution of Scielo, which plays a key role in the Southern hemisphere in making scientific knowledge more widely available. Japan is just a hair over 50% and given the margin of error of Adjusted OA may or may not have tipped to having a majority of papers in OA form.

Within the European Union, Green OA is more widely used in Portugal (16.3%), Ireland (15.8%), France (14.0%), and Belgium (13.8%), and least used in Lithuania (4.5%), Malta (5.0%), Croatia (5.2%), and Romania (5.3%).

Publishing in gold journals is much more frequently encountered in Eastern Europe, as it is much higher in Croatia, Slovenia, Latvia, Poland, Estonia, and Lithuania (in addition to Malta). One interesting hypothesis is that researchers in these countries may use Gold journals because they more frequently allow publishing in languages other than English. Should that be the case, this may also contribute to explaining the lower citation scores received by papers in Gold journals as the readership for 'vernacular languages', as Eugene Garfield (1998) would put it, is lower and the size of the potential reference pool is consequently also smaller. This is therefore potentially fertile ground for studying the social and linguistic aspects of science by examining where and why Gold open access journals are appearing and who actually makes use of them. The countries that least use Gold OA journals are France (6.6%), the United Kingdom (7.2%), and Belgium (7.4%).

IV-Discussion and policy implications of OA to scientific data and peer-reviewed articles

Somewhat like open access to scientific articles, open data is evolving rapidly in an environment where citizens, institutions, governments, non-profits, and private corporations loosely cooperate to develop infrastructure, standards, prototypes, and business models. From a government perspective, open data confers a competitive advantage in an increasingly information-based economy. New products and services can be developed directly from data or through extensive transformation adding value to the information.

Many organisations use their data as a source of revenue by providing paid access to their datasets. In the case of government agencies within the EU, a review has estimated that the direct revenues generated from the sale of government-owned data represent less than 1% of each agency's revenues. However, for a few organisations, the sale of data may represent close to 20% of revenue, which is likely to hinder the development of open data policies even if the data was generated using public funds. Still, the economic benefits of open data are estimated to outweigh sales revenue by approximately two orders of magnitude within the EU28.

The heterogeneous nature of scientific data is a challenge for the development of OA in this area. A few fields of research use highly standardised formats that facilitate the aggregation and reuse of data, with genomics, proteomics, chemical crystallography, geography, astronomy, and archaeology among them. The archiving of other, less standardised types of data needs to be carefully considered in order to generate datasets that will be usable by other researchers. Overall, the growth of OA scientific data as a valid, citable form of reference is limited by the difficulties associated with the standardisation of data and metadata formats, poor indexation by internet crawlers, and the scarcity of directories or registries that could make data more visible.

Whereas researchers have a 'natural incentive' to promote OA in the case of scholarly publications, as this makes their work more widely known, in some cases there might be negative incentives to make research data public. Researchers may indeed derive a competitive advantage by filling up their own data warehouse, and widely diffusing these data may limit the growth and curtail the size of their research enterprises. The comparatively slow growth of open scientific data may reflect the fact that some individuals are more eager to decry and act upon the adverse effects of self-interest as long as it is not their own.

The main bottlenecks that have prevented OA from gaining greater acceptance among stakeholders include a lack of awareness among researchers, concerns about the quality and prestige of OA journals, concerns and confusion about copyright, the dissuasive influence of article processing charges, difficulties moving beyond the current system of subscription-based journals, the lack of useful data on OA's evolution, a perceived lack of profitability surrounding OA business models, and a lack of infrastructure to support OA in developing countries. Despite these barriers, this investigation concludes that OA has become the dominant form of dissemination of peer-reviewed scholarly articles in the ERA, Brazil, Canada, Japan, and US.

Despite the presence of these barriers, this investigation concludes that OA has become the dominant form of dissemination of peer-reviewed scholarly articles in the ERA, Brazil, Canada, Japan, and US. Though only a few years ago research suggested that OA growth was modest, a series of studies conducted by Science-Metrix for the European Commission provides undeniable evidence that the OA movement is disruptive and that OA is traversing the scientific, technical and medical publishing industry with the speed and force of a tsunami.

It has been suggested that OA to scientific papers improves the speed, efficiency and efficacy of research by allowing researchers faster access to the information they need. It increases the visibility, usage of scientific impact of research. The model may help to relieve the 'serials crisis' and save the direct costs of print publication and dissemination. For authors, it can

shorten the delay between acceptance and publication in a journal. What is particularly interesting here is that the citation advantage is derived almost exclusively from the Green and Other OA portion, as Paid Access (not OA) systematically ranks behind Green OA and Other OA, and is an option yielding the lowest scientific impact (smaller number of citations received by papers on average) for seven fields. Publishing in Gold OA journals provides the least impactful choice in 15 out of 22 fields, and this low impact is probably more a reflection of the youth of these journals rather than anything else. Yet Gold OA journals beat Paid Access journals in 7 disciplines, showing that well-established Paid Access journals are losing their predominance and perhaps even their relevance in several fields of science. Despite their youth, Gold OA journals may continue to dislodge them in additional fields as their contents continue to improve. The day that articles that stay solely behind a pay wall will have lost their relevance may be edging closer faster than anyone expects.

Much has been said about the cost of publishing in Gold OA journals and for Gold OA articles ('hybrid publishing'). The cost of academic papers in the US is over \$100,000—which is calculated by dividing the higher education expenditures on R&D (HERD) by the number of papers published by academia. In addition to or included in this amount, a \$2,000 OA publication fee only accounts for a few percentage points of a typical research project budget, especially in the natural and health sciences. Green OA is free, and the majority of publishers accept that papers can be self-archived in one form or another (pre-print, post-print with final revision, or PDF) with no delay. Moreover, two-thirds of Gold OA journals do not levy author processing charges. There are free avenues to OA and cost should certainly not be seen as a barrier.

The current model of back end toll access is simply unsustainable because of its gross social inefficiency and ineffectiveness. Examining the OECD statistics on gross domestic expenditure on R&D in OECD and selected 'Non-OECD Member Economies' (Argentina, China, Romania, Russian Federation, Singapore, South Africa, Chinese Taipei), and using some conservative extrapolations, one can see that about \$400 billion were spent by governments (GovERD) to support R&D. The revenue generated by science, technical and medical publishing (STM) for English-speaking countries was worth approximately \$9.4 billion in the same year. Though these figures are not immediately comparable as part of the industry must derive income from non-English journals, the fact remains that a sizeable part of the research results paid for by \$400 billion in public money is either delayed, restricted, or still simply behind thick pay walls to generate only \$10 billion in private wealth. This is a case of gross inefficiency, one that taxpayers the world over should no longer tolerate.

Just as there is a need to continue to work vigilantly to remove the inefficiency created by all this public expenditure being made unavailable or available with undue restrictions, difficulties, and delays, there is also a need to closely monitor the effects of moving the scientific world from one based on Back End Paid Access (BEPA) to one based on Front End Paid Access (FEBA). BEPA created huge social inefficiency; FEBA has the potential to enlarge the rift between wealthier and more feebly financed countries, researchers, and scientific disciplines. Many mandates being promulgated at the moment run the risk of favouring a shift from BEPA to FEBA, from inaccessibility to inequality. Neither inaccessibility nor growing inequality are acceptable considering that universalism is one of the most beneficial values of scientific research.

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1 Introduction

Carried by the digital revolution, the movement towards open access (OA) to scholarly publications is transforming the global research communication and dissemination system. The popularity of OA has risen in response to the ineffectual situation whereby publicly funded research published in peer-reviewed journals continues to sit behind a 'pay wall,' a situation made worse by consistent increases in the price of scholarly journal subscriptions. This system, perceived by many as dysfunctional, has provided incentive to individual researchers, libraries, universities, research funders and governments to join the campaign for OA. Often characterised as a disruptive movement, OA continues to transform everything from publication processes to business models.

This situation led to parallel movements aimed at promoting OA on the one hand, for example through the development of OA policies, and at measuring and monitoring OA availability and its impact on the other hand. Quite early on, OA advocates used measurement to promote free availability, in particular after it was discovered that OA presented a 'citation advantage.' As a consequence, it is not always easy to distinguish what the authors of papers on OA are attempting to do: advocate for or measure OA.

The initial interest in the use of bibliometric methods in OA measurement focused on assessing the so-called citation advantage of OA¹ compared with subscription-based journals (Lawrence, 2001; Antelman, 2004; Harnad & Brody, 2004; Craig et al., 2007). Strong advocacy by authors such as Harnad (2003, 2008, 2012) suggested that benefits would ensue from so-called Green OA, that is, research papers self-archived by their authors in institutional repositories. Unsurprisingly, in this context, librarians and information scientists noted that they had a new mission, which was setting up and curating OA repositories (Prosser, 2003; Bailey, 2005; Chan, Kwok, & Yip, 2005; Chan, Devakos & Mircea, 2005; Repanovici, 2012).

Part of the OA literature has discussed how authors, researchers (Pelizzari, 2004; Swan & Brown, 2004; Dubini, Galimberti & Micheli, 2010) and publishers (Morris, 2003; Regazzi, 2004) would react to this new paradigm. Evidently, business and economic models were discussed (Bilder, 2003; Kurek, Geurts & Roosendaal, 2006; Houghton, 2010; Lakshmi Poorna, Mymoon & Hariharan, 2012), but there was also interest in which models academia and libraries would follow (Rowland et al., 2004; Swan et al., 2005; Hu, Zhang & Chen, 2010).

As OA continued to make inroads, a growing number of papers examined the state of development of OA in specific countries (Nyambi & Maynard, 2012; Sawant, 2012; Woutersen-Windhower, 2012; Miguel, Bongiovani, Gómez, & Bueno-de-la-Fuente, 2013) and in specific fields of research (Abad-García, Melero, Abadal & González-Teruel 2010; Gentil-Beccot, Mele, & Brooks, 2010; Charles, & Booth, 2011; Henderson, 2013). Yet, the measurement of the growth of OA has been hindered by a persistent lack of reliable data that would allow researchers to determine how OA has developed over time. Most studies examining the quantitative development of OA publishing have used variable methods and data sources that provide only brief snapshots of OA subsets for specific years (Laakso et al., 2011; Laakso & Björk, 2012).

Previous iterations of the research work behind this report have shown that freely available scientific papers published in peer-reviewed journals can take a wide variety of forms (e.g.

¹ An annotated bibliography is provided by Wagner (2010). <http://www.istl.org/10-winter/article2.html>

pre-print, HTML, PDF), be diffused through a wide range of media (e.g. institutional repositories, journal publishers' websites, content aggregators) and have varying levels of availability (immediate, delayed, transient), making simple definitions based on open access, Green and Gold no longer satisfactory. In addition to this need for more elaborate definitions, the authors of the previous version of this study received much feedback arguing that what was measured wasn't really open access. Though it took a while to realise this, current definitions of OA are frequently reshaped by advocates to suit the needs of the particular battles they are waging at any given moment.

For instance, though we had measured the same items as one of our critics who has published numerous papers in which he referred to these items as OA, it seemed that for him the definition of 'real' open access had shifted to be restricted to only those items with 'immediate availability.' Delayed OA frequently occurs when journal publishers make some papers or whole journal contents available for free only after an embargo period. However, it can also happen when authors encounter delays in self-archiving their papers, by, for example, being overly busy or not having an institutional repository in place, or simply because they are late converts to the idea of increasing the potential outcomes of their own research through OA. Placing immediacy as a criterion for earning the OA stamp seems to be overly restrictive, though one could say that this is one important quality of OA and should be accounted for in policies.

Some objections were also made to the effect that part of what we measured had a transient character—some papers do indeed come and go with respect to the freely available status. For example, in December 2012, Springer had a large promotion, part of which was to make many papers temporarily available. They were then later placed behind a pay wall. Most of the time, an item's transient availability is hardly known to a user who wants to download a paper. This is a quality of OA that should be reflected in policies, but should not be considered a condition to achieving the OA stamp.

Overall, what most transpired from the feedback received after the publication of the first version of this series of studies was the need for precise definitions of OA. Most conceptual representations of OA are derived from the established definitions provided in the three Bs:

- the Budapest Open Access Initiative (BOAI);²
- the Berlin Declaration on Open Access to Knowledge in the Sciences and Humanities;³ and
- the Bethesda Statement on Open Access Publishing.⁴

The Berlin Declaration and Bethesda Statement build on the definition developed in Budapest, which remains authoritative. BOAI defines OA as follows:

Free availability on the public internet, permitting any users to read, download, copy, distribute, print, search, or link to the full texts of these articles, crawl them for indexing, pass them as data to software, or use them for any other lawful purpose, without financial, legal, or technical barriers other than those inseparable from gaining access to the internet itself. The only constraint on reproduction and distribution, and

² <http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>.

³ <http://openaccess.mpg.de/286432/Berlin-Declaration>.

⁴ <http://legacy.earlham.edu/~peters/fos/bethesda.htm>.

the only role for copyright in this domain, should be to give authors control over the integrity of their work and the right to be properly acknowledged and cited.

Also, importantly, as the Wikipedia article on OA notes,⁵ "[i]n order to reflect actual practice in providing two different degrees of open access, the further distinction between gratis OA and libre OA was added in 2006," by Stevan Harnad and Peter Suber (Suber, 2008). The Wikipedia article mentions that "[g]ratis OA refers to free online access, and libre OA refers to free online access plus some additional re-use rights. The Budapest, Bethesda, and Berlin definitions had corresponded only to libre OA." More specifically, Suber (2012) proposed the following definitions:

Gratis OA—access that is free of charge but not necessarily free of copyright and licensing restrictions (users must seek permission to exceed fair use). Gratis OA removes price barriers but not permission barriers.

Libre OA—access that is both free of charge (gratis OA) and free of at least some copyright and licensing restrictions. Users have permission to exceed fair use, at least in certain ways. Libre OA removes price barriers and at least some permission barriers.

The use of the terms "not necessarily" and "of at least some" implies uncertainties. Moreover, there are more than "two different degrees of open access." This explains why the following binary definitions were preferred in the present series of reports produced by Science-Metrix for the European Commission.

A: Access—can be open (free), restricted or paid; with unrestricted or restricted usage rights; quality controlled or not; pre-print (pre-referring), post-print (post-referring), or published version (with final copy editing and page layout); immediate or delayed; permanent or transient.

OA: Open Access—freely available online to all.

IOA: Ideal OA—free; quality controlled (peer-reviewed or editorially controlled); with unrestricted usage rights (e.g. CC BY); in final, published form; immediate; permanent.

RA: Restricted Access—access restricted to members of a group, club, or society.

PA: Paid Access—access restricted by a pay wall; includes subscription access, licensed access, and pay-to-view access.

Restricted OA—free but with download restrictions (e.g. registration required, restricted to manual download, HTML-only as opposed to self-contained format such as PDF) or re-use rights (e.g. CC NC).

Green OA—OA provided before or immediately after publication by author self-archiving.

Gold OA—immediate OA provided by a publisher, sometimes with paid for publication fee. Note that several Gold journals have right restriction: they are Gold ROA. For example, of the 38% of journals listed in the DOAJ that use a Creative Common licence, only 53% use the CC-BY licence that would allow them to qualify for the IOA definition above (Herb, 2014).

Gold OA Journal—journal offering immediate cover-to-cover access.

⁵ http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Open_access.

Gold OA Article—immediately accessible paper appearing in a Gold journal, or in a PA journal (the latter is also sometimes referred to as hybrid open access).

ROA: Robin Hood OA or Rogue OA—Available for free in spite of restrictions, usage rights, or copyrights (overriding RA, PA, Restricted OA). As the publishers' copyright policies and self-archiving rules are compiled by the University of Nottingham in the SHERPA/RoMEO database, Rogue OA is synonymous with Robin Hood OA.

DOA: Delayed OA—access after a delay period or embargo.

Delayed Green OA—free online access provided by the author after a delay (due to author's own delay to make available for free) or embargo period (typically imposed by publisher).

Delayed Gold OA—free online access provided by the publisher after a delay (e.g. change of policy that makes contents available for free) or embargo period.

Delayed Gold OA Journal—Journal offering cover-to-cover access after an embargo period or after a delay.

Delayed Gold OA Article—Paper appearing in a Gold journal or in a PA journal (the latter is also sometimes referred to as hybrid open access) which is available after an embargo period or after a delay.

TOA: Transient OA—free online access during a certain time.

Transient Green OA—free online access provided by the author for a certain time which then disappears. Note that a substantial part of Green OA could be Transient Green OA due to the unstable nature of the internet, websites, and institutional repositories, many of which are not updated or maintained after a period of time and are therefore susceptible to deletion in subsequent institutional website overhauls. There are also integrator repositories that can change access rules, for example after being acquired by a third party.

Transient Gold OA—free but temporary online access provided by the publisher, instead of permanent. Sometimes appears as part of promotion. Note that some Gold journals and articles sometimes become paid access after a certain time, because of revised strategies by a publisher or because they are sold to another publisher who reinstates paid access.

The availability of solid evidence on the status of OA is crucial for decision-makers in research institutions, funding bodies and governments, as well as for publishers who aim to maximize the positive impacts of their initiatives aimed at providing outlets, guidance, or incentive for the OA dissemination of peer-reviewed publications, such as the adoption of OA policies and the development of repositories or Gold OA journals. For instance, knowing how common OA is today, how fast its share is growing and what proportion of journal articles are currently OA, are key questions that they must address for adapting their strategies

It is in this context that Science-Metrix was commissioned by the European Commission to measure and monitor nearly all aspects of OA, such as the development of OA strategies for free access to scientific publications (Section 2) and scientific data (Section 3) as well as the increase in the share of scholarly publications available in OA (Section 4). This report ends with a discussion of the potential policy implications of this study's findings (Section 5).

2 Policies on open access—free access to scientific publications

Initially, a review of national legislation, policies and initiatives (Section 2.1) as well as of funders' policies (Section 2.2) pertaining to OA are presented. Subsequently, the various strategies adopted by research institutions to promote OA (Section 2.3) and publishers' responses to OA (Section 2.4) are presented.

2.1 National legislation, policies and initiatives

In the last decade, governments have demonstrated their growing awareness of the benefits of OA and have taken concrete steps to support greater access to the published results of research, particularly research funded by taxpayer dollars. Indeed, the potential impacts of implementing OA strategies are great—OA accelerates and broadens opportunities for the adoption and commercialisation of research findings, leading to increased returns on public investment in research and development (R&D) and on private investment. This, in turn, may lead to greater productivity in certain sectors of the economy and the potential for the emergence of new industries based upon OA content (e.g., new industries that are built on publicly accessible data). OA may also have positive impacts on policy development through better informed debate and enhanced access to the information underpinning policy decisions (Houghton & Sheehan, 2009).

2.1.1 National legislation

Most national governments have not proposed or implemented direct legislation on OA. Instead, OA is often addressed through less formal means, such as the production of guidelines for research-funding agencies. Related legislation often includes laws on copyright and licensing; in fact, all countries covered in this study—with the exception of Cyprus—have copyright legislation that may apply to peer-reviewed publications. Legislation directly addressing OA has been implemented in the US, Spain and Germany. Italy and Lithuania have also recently passed laws that have direct implications for OA in those countries.

United States: The Consolidated Appropriations Act, 2008 (H.R. 2764), is the legislative basis for the OA policy of the National Institutes of Health (NIH). With this legislation, the US became the first country to adopt a national OA mandate. The policy states that all NIH-funded researchers must submit an electronic version of their final, peer-reviewed manuscripts to the National Library of Medicine's PubMed Central no later than 12 months after the official date of publication.

Proposed in 2006, 2010 and again in 2012, the Federal Research Public Access Act (FRPAA) would have required that the 11 federal agencies with research expenditures over US\$100 million create online repositories of journal articles of their research and make them publicly available. However, FRPAA was never voted on and was succeeded by the Fair Access to Science and Technology Research Act (FASTR), which was introduced in Congress in February 2013.

In the same month, the White House's Office of Science and Technology Policy (OSTP) issued a Directive on Public Access. Both require all federal agencies with extramural research expenditures of over US\$100 million (24 federal agencies in total) to develop a federal research public access policy.

In September 2013, new public access legislation was introduced in the US House of Representatives—the Public Access to Public Science Act (PAPS)—which intends to build on

the OSTP Directive on Public Access. At the time of writing, it has not been introduced in the Senate. On January 17, 2014, an omnibus federal spending bill also similar in concept to the OSTP Directive was signed into law by President Obama that includes an OA mandate. Section 527 of the Consolidated Appropriations Act, 2014 (H.R. 3547) states that agencies that have research budgets of US\$100 million or more operating under the portion of the bill covering Labor, Health and Human Services, and Education are required to provide online access to peer-reviewed articles that report on federally funded research within 12 months of publication.

Legislation is also being enacted at the state level, such as in Illinois (Open Access to Research Articles Act [Senate Bill 1900]), New York (New York State Taxpayer Access to Publicly Funded Research Act [A 180/S 4050]) and California (California Taxpayer Access to Publicly Funded Research Act [AB 609]).

Spain: Spain passed the national Law on Science, Technology and Innovation (2011) (Ley de la Ciencia). Under Article 37, titled “Open Access Dissemination,” the law mandates that a digital version of the final copy of research accepted for publication and funded under the national public R&D funding scheme be deposited within 12 months of publication in an OA repository. Additionally, two autonomous regional governments—the Autonomous Community of Madrid (2008) and the Principality of Asturias (2009)—have established OA mandates promoting the population of open repositories with peer-reviewed scientific articles (European Commission, 2011).

Germany: A new German national law (BGB1. I S. 3714) was enacted on October 1, 2013, that modified Section 38 of the German Copyright Act. The copyright reform directly targets OA to scientific publications; more specifically, it is meant to hold up a ‘second publication right’ for authors, allowing them to make any of their articles stemming from publicly funded research openly accessible and available for non-commercial purposes without the consent of the publishers 12 months after the first publication.⁶

Italy: Italy’s Law of 7 October 2013 (no. 112) includes a regulation for OA to scientific publications. Researchers whose research has been publicly funded (at least 50%) are required to either publish their work in an OA journal or deposit their work in OA archives no later than 18 months from the first publication for scientific, technical and medical disciplines or 24 months for the humanities and social sciences.⁷

Lithuania: In Lithuania, national legislation (Article 45 of the 2009 Law on Science and Studies of the Republic of Lithuania⁸) took effect on May 12, 2009, that mandates that all state-funded research be made publicly available via the internet and other means.

Legislation has also been proposed in Brazil, Poland and Denmark.

Brazil: A bill (PL 1120/2007) introduced in May 2007 proposed that all public institutions of higher education and research units be required to establish institutional repositories, where all technical and scientific research outputs would be deposited and made freely available

⁶ Buch Report. (2013, June). *Green light for green way* [article].

http://www.buchreport.de/nachrichten/verlage/verlage_nachricht/datum/2013/06/28/gruenes-licht-fuer-gruenen-weg.htm?utm_source=twitterfeed&utm_medium=twitter

⁷ Moscon, V. (2013). *Italy: Open access in Italy* [article].

<http://merlin.obs.coe.int/iris/2014/1/article32.en.html>

⁸ Republic of Lithuania. (2009, April). *Republic of Lithuania Law on Higher Education and Research* [Web document]. http://www3.lrs.lt/pls/inter3/dokpaieska.showdoc_l?p_id=366717

online.⁹ Although the bill was approved by the relevant committees, it was ultimately archived in January 2012.

Poland: In January of 2013, the Polish Ministry of Administration and Digitisation published Draft Guidelines for the Proposal of the Act on Open Public Resources.¹⁰ The aim of the draft bill is to ensure that as much material as possible, particularly that resulting from public subsidies, is made openly accessible on the internet. The law would apply to all publicly funded scientific, educational and cultural resources.

Denmark: In March 2011, Denmark's Open Access Committee issued a series of OA policy recommendations (Danish Agency for Libraries and Media, 2011). The paper includes 16 recommendations in total, the first being that "a national Open Access policy be phrased on the basis of Green Open Access with continual quality assurance by the scientific journals" and that "there should be Open Access to the results of publicly funded research to as great an extent as possible." A series of meetings have since been launched with stakeholders in order to develop a Danish OA strategy.

2.1.2 National policies and initiatives

A number of countries in the European Research Area (ERA) have instituted national policies, programmes and principles related to OA. The following are some of the more notable OA initiatives being undertaken in these countries.

United Kingdom: The UK is a leader in the development of OA to peer-reviewed publications, having assumed a highly proactive stance in recent years. The UK Government stated its commitment to OA in its Innovation & Research Strategy for Growth in December 2011 (Department for Business Innovation and Skills [BIS], 2014) and the Higher Education Funding Council for England (HEFCE) and Research Councils UK (RCUK) have long pushed for greater public access to publicly supported research. In July 2013, the HEFCE, on behalf of all four UK higher education funding bodies, issued a consultation on OA in the next Research Excellence Framework (REF). The HEFCE is currently exploring how to make OA a requirement so that research outputs submitted to any research assessment exercise after 2014 are as widely accessible as possible.¹¹ Jisc, a UK registered charity that aims to champion the use of digital technologies in UK education and research, has also had a considerable influence. Jisc has funded major OA projects that encompass content, infrastructure, management and training, including SHERPA, the Registry of Open Access Repositories (ROAR), the Directory of Open Access Repositories (*OpenDOAR*), the Repository Support Project, the Open Repository Junction and ePrints UK.

One of the most influential projects is the 2012 "Finch Report" on the awareness of and discussion surrounding OA in the country. The Working Group on Expanding Access to Published Research Findings, chaired by Dame Janet Finch, was formed in 2011 with the goal of proposing a programme of action to broaden access to research findings and outcomes

⁹ Brazil House of Representatives. (2007). *PL 1120/2007, Projeto de Lei* [Web document]. <http://www.camara.gov.br/proposicoesWeb/fichadetramitacao?idProposicao=352237>

¹⁰ Polish Ministry of Administration and Digitization. (2012, December). *Draft guidelines for the proposal of the act on open public resources* [Web document]. <http://mac.bip.gov.pl/prawo-i-prace-legislacyjne/projekt-zalozen-projektu-ustawy-o-otwartych-zasobach-publicznych.html>

¹¹ HEFCE. (2014). *Open access and research assessment* [Web document]. <https://www.hefce.ac.uk/whatwedo/rsrch/rinfrastruct/oa/>

(Research Information Network, 2011). The Working Group, supported by the Department of Business, Innovation and Skills (BIS), the Publishers Association, RCUK and the HEFCE, presented its findings and recommendations in June 2012 (Finch, 2012). Notably, the Working Group strongly advocated Gold OA based on article processing charges (APCs) (though Green OA was also allowed, with embargoes).

While the report was controversial, the UK government formally accepted most of its recommendations in July 2012, resulting in rapid institutional uptake. The Policy on Open Access, which came into force on April 1, 2013, expresses the RCUK's preference for immediate OA with maximum opportunity for re-use. It will make all UK government-funded research OA within five years, with a target of 45% in the first year. In September 2013, a report from the BIS Committee was released (BIS, 2013). The report asked that the UK government and the RCUK reconsider their preference for Gold OA, echoing widespread concerns that the preference for Gold OA did not reflect policy being adopted in other nations and that the UK OA initiatives would lead to significant cost increases for the UK.¹²

The Finch Group published a review in October 2013 of the progress that had been made to date in implementing the recommendations of the Finch Report (Finch, 2013). The report stated that progress "has been mixed, and has given rise to issues and problems that have not as yet been fully resolved." The Finch Group reaffirmed its support for a mixed economy (both Gold and Green OA) and noted policy similarities across countries and issued 14 additional recommendations. In January 2014, the UK government published a response to the Finch Group's review on OA implementation, upholding its commitment to an OA policy with a "strong preference for Gold OA and an acceptance of Green OA" (Willets, 2014). In response to one of the key recommendations of the Finch Group, the new 'Access to Research' plan was announced in February 2014, making thousands of research journal articles available for free at libraries across the UK, but only on computers located physically within a public library (walk-in access).¹³

Ireland: Ireland's National Principles for Open Access Policy Statement was released on October 23, 2012. The outputs of all research fully or partially funded by the Irish government, including peer-reviewed publications, research data and other research artefacts, are to be deposited in OA repositories. Although embargoes and restrictions may apply, the full text is recommended to be released no later than the publication date and the metadata is to be released immediately after deposit. Publication in OA journals is encouraged but is neither mandatory nor a substitute for deposit in a suitable repository. Ireland's universities benefit from a pre-existing network of interoperable institutional repositories with a national portal established as a separate project from 2007 to 2010.

Sweden: Since 2006, Sweden has had a national OA programme, OpenAccess.se, which has played a role in the creation of a national search portal for scholarly publications (SwePub), the Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ) and a number of institutional and funder policies. The programme's steering committee called on the Ministry of Education to develop a national OA policy in 2011. In the Swedish Research and Innovation Bill for 2013–2016, the government commissioned the Swedish Research Council to develop national OA guidelines.

¹² Brienza, C. (2014, January 30). *Paying twice or paying thrice? Open access publishing in a global system of scholarly knowledge production and consumption* [article].

<http://blogs.lse.ac.uk/impactofsocialsciences/2014/01/30/paying-twice-or-paying-thrice-brienza/>

¹³ Clark, I. (2014, February 20). *U.K. libraries offer free article access to walk-ins* [article].

<http://lj.libraryjournal.com/2014/02/oa/u-k-libraries-offer-free-article-access-to-walk-ins/>

The first version of the guidelines is expected to be in place by the end of 2014 (Kronman, 2012).

France: France's HAL multi-disciplinary open archive was launched by the Centre national de la recherche scientifique (CNRS) in 2001. In 2006, the CNRS, along with five other governmental research centres, the *Conférence des présidents d'universités*, the *Institut Pasteur* and the *Conférence des grandes écoles*, agreed to coordinate a national strategy for OA archiving of scientific production using HAL. In contrast to this strong OA infrastructure, no OA mandate emanating from national research funding organisations exists in France, with the exception of the social sciences and humanities branch of the Agence nationale de la recherche; thus, compliance with existing policies is still voluntary.

Croatia: Croatia does not currently have an OA mandate at the national level. However, the Ministry of Science Education and Sports supports Hrcak, the portal of scientific journals of Croatia. Hrcak is a gateway to 327 OA journals and over 90,000 full text articles.

Europe: At the pan-European level, the Open Access Pilot was launched by the European Commission as part of its Seventh Framework Programme (FP7) in August 2008. Within several thematic areas of the framework programme, FP7 projects are required to deposit peer-reviewed research articles or final manuscripts resulting from projects into an online repository.

Other Europe-wide initiatives include the Digital Repository Infrastructure Vision for European Research (DRIVER), established to build a cohesive network of repositories for research and education, and the Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe (OpenAIRE), a complementary project offering organisational and technological infrastructure for the identification, deposition, access and monitoring of FP7- and European Research Council (ERC)-funded publications. Launched in February 2014, a new 30-month project titled PASTEUR4OA (Open Access Policy Alignment Strategies for European Union Research) aims to help Member States develop and/or reinforce OA strategies and policies at the national level and facilitate coordination among the Member States.

2.1.3 National uptake of open access

Within the ERA, Brazil, Canada, Japan and the US, 118 million records are spread across 1,770 repositories (as registered in *OpenDOAR* in April 2014). Their distribution per country is shown in Figure 1. Countries above the regression line, such as Lithuania, Switzerland and the UK, have proportionately more records given the number of repositories they have while those below the line, such as Israel, Norway, Bulgaria, Romania and Austria, have comparatively smaller repositories relative to other countries. Liechtenstein, Malta and Slovakia did not have any repositories listed in *OpenDOAR* at the time of writing. Nine countries—Israel, Romania, Bulgaria, Macedonia, Luxembourg, Cyprus, Latvia, Iceland and Austria—have less than 30,000 records in their respective repositories.

2.2 Funders' policies and initiatives

Research funding bodies seek maximum impact from the research they support, which can best be achieved by ensuring the widespread accessibility of publications arising from that research. Prominent examples of a funder's mandate are those of the Wellcome Trust, a UK-based charitable foundation (which established the first policy of its kind in the world in 2006), and the US National Institutes of Health (NIH), both of which require grant recipients to make funded research publicly available (published in an Open Access journal or deposited in a repository) within a specified timeframe.

Figure 1 Uptake of open access by country as illustrated by the number of repositories and number of records, April 2014

Source: Compiled by Science-Metrix from *OpenDOAR*.

Major international research performing and funding organisations are also playing a key role in the spread of OA by implementing their own policies ensuring free access to their publications. These include the World Bank, the United Nations Organization for Education, Science and Culture (UNESCO), the European Research Council (ERC), the World Health Organization (WHO).

An analysis of funding bodies' OA policies was performed using data from the SHERPA-maintained JULIET database, as well as the BioMed Central (Funder Policies), Registry of Open Access Repositories Mandatory Archiving Policies (ROARMAP) and MELIBEA databases. The goal of this analysis was to assess the extensiveness of OA policies as well as to examine OA rules for grant recipients, across ERA countries and in Brazil, Canada, Japan and the US. The OA policies reviewed below encompass any publicly available official statement inciting researchers to make their research publicly available, regardless of re-use permissions, restrictions or embargoes.

The country with the highest number of OA policies is the UK (with 34 mandates), followed by Canada (14), the US (9), Denmark (6), Ireland (5) and France (5). No funder mandates could be found for Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Estonia, Finland, Greece, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, Poland, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Liechtenstein, Turkey, or the Former Yugoslav Republic of Macedonia. The situation is unclear for Israel. Even though there is no official OA mandate or proposed policy in Israel, BioMed Central's list of policies states that the Israel Science Foundation's grant funds may be used to cover APCs.¹⁴ Caution should be taken in interpreting the number of OA policies across countries.

The number of policies alone is a weak indicator of commitment to OA in a given country. Other factors to consider are the scope of existing policies, whether OA is encouraged or

¹⁴ <http://www.biomedcentral.com/funding/funderpolicies>

required, whether a policy is proposed or implemented, and other critical characteristics, limitations and exceptions to be found in funder policies. An analysis of 48 implemented policies was conducted, with startling inequalities found in the level of detail provided. Funding agencies that are building a new OA policy or renewing a pre-existing policy should consider a number of key points for transparency. Among these are:

- **Coverage of article processing charges (APCs):** When trying to determine whether funders would pay APCs (as part of the grants or separately), Science-Metrix found that over 40% of policies made no mention of them. The remaining 46% of funders indicated that they would cover the APCs, and 13% indicated that they would not.
- **Preference for Green or Gold OA:** Except for the UK, none of the funder policies favoured Gold OA, about 40% favoured Green, 2% mandated both Green and Gold and 58% expressed no preference. If Green OA is allowed, specific repositories may be identified. For example, all research supported by the Wellcome Trust, the NIH, Arthritis Research UK, the British Heart Foundation, Cancer Research UK, the Chief Scientist Office of the Scottish Government Health and Social Care Directorate, the UK Department of Health, and Telethon Italy must be available through PubMed Central (PMC, UKPMC or Europe PMC).
- **Acceptable types of documents and metadata:** Policies commonly refer to the post-print version, although this expression may be interpreted as the final peer-reviewed manuscript or as the publisher's version; in total, 79% of policies specified that articles should be deposited in their final accepted version or post-print.
- **Project scope:** Guidelines must clarify at what point the policy applies with respect to a certain percentage of funding provided or the number of authors who are grantees.
- **Embargoes:** If the policy supports Green OA, embargoes may be accepted to give publishers exclusivity for a limited time. Among the 48 funder policies reviewed, 77% accepted embargoes between 6 and 12 months.
- **Compliance:** Expectations relative to policy compliance is seldom tracked or reported.

Other items that may be listed in the policy include the prescribed timing of deposits, exceptions in types of outputs, the transfer of rights, and sanctions.

2.3 Research institutions' strategies for OA

Universities and research institutes often lead OA initiatives, and many have participated in international agreements and declarations that promote OA (e.g., the Coalition of Open Access Policy Institutions [COAPI] and the Compact for Open Access Publishing Equity [COAPE]). Universities are chiefly concerned with managing their intellectual assets (not only articles but datasets, course materials and research papers), enhancing their competitive profile by showcasing their research output and maximising and attracting research income and performance. As such, they are setting up institutional digital repositories to preserve and distribute faculty scholarly articles and other research outputs, and they are requesting or requiring that researchers deposit their research in institutional repositories or participate in a shared repository. Universities are also pioneering software and application development for OA repositories. In terms of Gold OA, many universities have set aside earmarked funds for the purposes of OA provision (for example, to help authors pay for APCs) and some publishers may accept author requests to waive these fees.

In a survey of head librarians at universities and higher learning institutions conducted by Science-Metrix, 73% of respondents agreed or strongly agreed with the statement that "Providing open access to scholarly publications is a priority in [their] organisation." A similar proportion (i.e., 70%) agreed or strongly agreed with the statement that "Providing open

access to scholarly publications is a priority in [their] country.” However, only 42% of these respondents stated that their organisation has an OA policy regarding peer-reviewed scholarly publications. This discrepancy could be attributed to a number of factors, including delays in the elaboration and adoption of an OA policy, the decision to adopt a voluntary approach to OA, or the existence of OA policies aimed at other types of research outputs (such as theses or data). Among the respondents whose institutions have an OA policy, 22% declared that it is not publicly available. This suggests that there may be relatively large gaps in institutional OA policies’ databases.

Fewer databases exist for institutional OA policies than for funders’ OA policies. Only ROARMAP and MELIBEA maintain extensive lists. According to these directories, Brazil, Canada, Japan, the US and ERA countries collectively have 293 institutional, multi-institutional, sub-institutional and thesis OA mandates presently in place, a substantial increase from the 231 in ROARMAP a year ago. The largest number of mandates is in the US, followed by the UK, Italy, Finland and Portugal. No such mandates appear in the databases used in this study for the following countries: Austria, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Estonia, Israel, Latvia, Liechtenstein, Macedonia, Malta, Romania and Slovakia.

Brazil, Canada, Japan, the US and the ERA countries collectively have 70 proposed institutional, multi-institutional, sub-institutional OA mandates and non-mandates. No such propositions appear in the databases used in this study for the following countries: Bulgaria, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, Greece, Hungary, Iceland, Ireland, Israel, Latvia, Liechtenstein, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Macedonia, Malta, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Switzerland and Turkey.

A few institutions stand out by virtue of the specific programmes they developed to understand, measure or promote the adoption of OA in scholarly literature, furthering the development of OA culture through these initiatives. Prominent examples include:

- **The University of Southampton:** Home to ROAR and ROARMAP, the University’s School of Electronics and Computer Science adopted its OA mandate, the first of its kind, in 2002. The entire institution followed suit in 2006, mandating all research to be deposited in its repository.¹⁵
- **The European Organization for Nuclear Research (CERN):** CERN implemented a self-archiving policy in 2003 and has encouraged publication in OA journals in the field of physics since 2005. It recently launched the Sponsoring Consortium for Open Access Publishing in Particle Physics (SCOAP3) initiative. Billed as the “largest single global Open Access initiative built to date,” SCOAP3 has library and publishing partners from 24 countries around the world. It encompasses a new model in which the APCs will not be paid by authors or even their institutions, but by the consortium, and aims to convert a dozen of the leading journals in high energy physics, in full or partially, to APC-funded OA.¹⁶
- **The University of Minho:** A pioneer of institutional repositories within the ERA, the University established its repository in 2003 and adopted its OA mandate at the end of 2004. It has also organised several OA conferences, seminars and workshops.

¹⁵ University of Southampton. (2013). *ePrints Soton* [Web page]. <http://www.southampton.ac.uk/library/research/eprints/>

¹⁶ SCOAP3. (2014). SCOAP3 – Sponsoring Consortium for Open Access Publishing In Particle Physics [Web page]. <http://scoap3.org/what-is-scoap3>

- **The University of Nottingham:** Since 2002, the University has led the SHERPA partnership, which operates RoMEO, JULIET and *OpenDOAR*. As such, the university has played an important part in the establishment of OA repositories by testing, evaluating and disseminating ideas for new developments in the field. The university's own OA mandate was adopted in 2009.
- **Harvard University:** The University's Berkman Center for Internet and Society is home to the Harvard Open Access Project (HOAP), led by Peter Suber, one of OA's most vocal advocates. The Project's goals include conducting research and policy analysis on OA, providing timely and accurate information about OA, and fostering OA within the university and beyond. Surprisingly, the University does not have an institution-wide OA policy, but 8 out of 9 schools adhere to the proposed policy.¹⁷
- **Cornell University:** The University co-owns and operates arXiv, one of the most important OA repositories in existence. A resolution was also passed on scholarly publishing in May 2005 encouraging (but not requiring) all faculty to negotiate their intellectual property rights with the journals in which they publish.¹⁸

2.3.1 Effects of institutional strategies for OA

Within the ERA, Brazil, Canada, Japan and the US, nearly 40 million records are spread across 1,450 institutional repositories as of April 2014 in *OpenDOAR* alone. Institutional repositories account for 28% of records in OA repositories (disciplinary repositories account for 38%, governmental repositories for 25% and aggregating repositories for 9%) (as of April 2013).

Not surprisingly, according to *OpenDOAR* data, many of the largest institutional repositories in the world are located in universities, and more particularly in the US—such as at the University of Michigan and Yale University. The largest university repository in Europe is located at the Technical University of Gelsenkirchen in Germany, followed by the Katholieke Universiteit Leuven in Belgium and University College London in the UK. The largest institutional repository overall is English Heritage, dwarfing all others with 8 million items, compared to 2.5 million at the University of Michigan, the next largest repository.

The survey of head librarians at universities and higher learning institutions conducted by Science-Metrix asked respondents to identify all repository types maintained by their institution for OA scholarly publications. Nearly three-quarters (72%) of respondents selected central repositories, suggesting that many institutions appear to have at least one OA repository in spite of the absence of OA policy. Only 15% of respondents indicated that their institution has no institutional repository or systematic archiving.

2.3.2 Challenges in the development of institutional repositories and implementation of institutional policies

Repository infrastructure development and implementation faces numerous challenges related to intellectual property rights, data curation, embargo management, author authentication for repository deposit and long-term preservation. Another challenge pertains to the non-uniformity of manuscript files and metadata formats. Repository contents are in

¹⁷ Presidents and Fellows of Harvard College. (2010). *Open access policies*. <http://osc.hul.harvard.edu/policies#participating>

¹⁸ Cornell University. (2009). Copyright management [Web document]. http://copyright.cornell.edu/policies/copyright_management.cfm

many ways heterogeneous. Most repositories now adhere to a set of internationally agreed upon technical standards to standardise the metadata used to identify each item they contain, allowing their contents to be indexed and harvested through the OAI-PMH (an OA harvesting protocol). The quality of the IT infrastructure is also less variable now than it was a decade ago. Nearly all mid-sized and small subject repositories have been built using open source solutions and are currently run using openly available repository software such as Eprints, D-Space and Opus (Björk, 2013).

The interoperability of repositories—allowing all types of repositories to communicate and connect with one another and transfer information, metadata and digital objects between each other—is another technical challenge. Repository development is undergoing rapid change, contributing to an “evolving interoperability landscape that at first sight may appear chaotic, confusing, and complex” (Confederation of Open Access Repositories [COAR], 2012). The European Commission, for example, reports that many European national repository infrastructures have been created but are at risk of remaining “islands” that are not sufficiently interconnected (European Commission, 2011). To enable greater interoperability, guidelines, protocols and standards are currently being written.

Another noted challenge, this one impacting the implementation of institutional policies, is the promotion of OA within the academic community. Incentives are essential for reaching researchers who are reticent about OA or are deterred by the trade-off between the costs and benefits of making their work OA. In the survey of head librarians at universities and higher learning institutions conducted by Science-Metrix, respondents were asked to identify every type of incentive used to promote OA publication and archiving of scholarly publications in their organisation. Survey results suggest that direct advantages for researchers who make their work available in OA form remain rare at the level of institutions. Of survey respondents, 49% indicated that researchers in their organisation were encouraged to archive their scholarly work but without any formal reward, and 36% indicated that their institution had no policy in this regard. Only 15% of respondents indicated that self-archiving was mandatory and 14% indicated that financial support was available for researchers who published in OA journals.

2.4 Responses from scientific journal publishers

As publishers’ income is traditionally generated via subscription, it is commonly assumed that there exist many vested interests to preserve the status quo of the current subscription market. However, many publishers have recognised that OA can lead to wider dissemination, maximised market reach, greater visibility and higher journal citation impact factor of their articles. Scholarly societies that were previously hesitant to embrace OA, including the American Association for the Advancement of Science (AAAS) and the Royal Society, have recently made announcements or established initiatives in support of OA.¹⁹ Publishers are currently exploring a variety of OA options and seeking the most effective business model to respond to rapidly evolving market expectations.

Several models for OA publishing have emerged that differ with respect to the type of content access, the retention of authors’ rights and the type of financing. These models include: OA journals that are free for authors and readers; OA journals that are free for

¹⁹ Joseph, H. (2014). *The White House Directive: One year in, time for further action* [article]. <http://www.sparc.arl.org/blog/white-house-directive-one-year-time-further-action>

authors and readers of the online version, with subscription payment for the paper version; ‘author pays’ OA journals; hybrid systems; journals with free access to certain content; and journals with free access to contents after a period of embargo (Abad, 2009). Most of the growth in OA publishing has come from newly founded OA journals that charge authors or their organisations for the publishing services (the APC model), a proven business model. In lieu of subscription costs being met by readers, their financial survival depends on a mix of funding sources in various combinations, including (Crow, 2009; Eckman & Weil, 2010; Frantsvåg, 2010; Friend, 2011): APCs, public or charitable research funding bodies, institutional support, grants and subsidies, endowments, sponsorships, collaborative purchasing, hard copy support and advertising revenues.

In recent years, many traditional commercial publishers—including the Nature Publishing Group, Springer and Elsevier—have established sizable OA journal operations or have extended their hybrid OA operations. Successful ‘Mega-OA’ journals have also been established, most notably PLoS ONE (Public Library of Science) and Scientific Reports (Nature Publishing Group), that have had a positive impact on the credibility of OA peer-reviewed publications. Revenues from the PLoS journals have exceeded the organisation’s expenses since 2010. However, adoption of the Gold model has been rather slow. Laakso et al. (2011) reported that, in 2009, the share of all peer-reviewed journal articles in OA journals had reached 7.7%. The big publishers are not converting their journals to OA on a broader scale, likely because they are not being threatened yet by significant reductions in their subscription income. Between 2005 and 2011, Elsevier increased its operating profit margin from 31% to 37%, Informa (which includes Taylor & Francis), from 25% to 36%, Wolters Kluwer Health, from 16% to 20%, and John Wiley STM, for the period 2008–2011, from 39% to 43% (Björk, 2013). These publishers are still profiting from multi-year ‘big deal’ e-licenses.

Journal publishers are also increasingly allowing article archiving. From January 2004 to December 2012, the number of publishers’ OA policies that allow some form of archiving grew steadily, from 80 to 1,425. Of these, 33% allow post-print archiving, 9% allow pre-print archiving only and 31% (including Gold OA journals) allow pre-print and post-print archiving. The remaining 28% of publishers do not formally allow any form of archiving but may agree to special arrangements with authors, particularly in the context of a funder mandate.

2.4.1 Impacts of publishers’ strategies on authors

The research life cycle begins with authors, the initial copyright holders of the publications, and authors will ultimately decide whether OA becomes popular. Authors, academics and researchers want widespread visibility for their research outputs, ideally in high-status journals that maximise their chances of securing high impact and research grants. OA journals can provide that, as well as time savings, as they can reduce the delay between acceptance and publication in a journal.

Interestingly, results of researcher surveys, including the European SOAP (Study of Open Access Publishing) project (Dallmeier-Tiessen et al., 2011) and the Survey on Scientific Information in the Digital Age (European Commission, 2007), have shown that there is widespread support for OA as a principle among researchers, in particular the idea that publicly funded research should be OA. However, surveys also demonstrate that researchers rank other considerations as more important than a journal’s OA policies, including speed of publication, quality of peer review and the journal’s scientific impact (Bird, 2010), although funders’ and institutions’ mandates are increasingly influencing authors’ choices of where to publish.

Take-up of Green OA has remained relatively low, with the percentage in studies estimated to be around 20%. Elsevier has recently reported that the Green archiving of accepted manuscripts remains at 4–5% (Morgan, Campbell & Teleen, 2012). Considerable disciplinary variation can be seen: the share of OA in the arts stands at 10%, while this number is 45% in mathematics (Gargouri et al., 2011).

2.4.2 Impacts of publishers' strategies on libraries

In response to the changing landscape of scholarly communication, publishers developed new products known as 'big deals.' Contracts are established between libraries and publishers whereby libraries secure access to a large set of journals distributed by the publisher, mostly in electronic format, for all faculty and students at the subscribing university, for a set price and for a period of three to five years. As the prices of serials have continued to rise faster than inflation, library budgets have increased moderately, stagnated or even decreased, a situation referred to as the 'serials crisis.' Since the beginning of the crisis, mergers and acquisitions in the scholarly communication sector have increased the concentration of journals in the hands of a limited number of publishers. Librarians contend that even though they get more journals than ever before, a sizeable proportion of these are unwanted and subscribed to in order to get a reasonable price for the journals they need. Even if the price per unit is low, their overall budget has been stretched to its limit. In short, librarians have little power to opt out of big deals or negotiate the terms of subscriptions contracts.

Librarians have been in the vanguard in fighting increases in journal costs and promoting the development of repositories. Results from surveys of academic librarians (Greyson et al., 2009; Palmer, Dill & Christie, 2009) have shown that librarians feel a strong sense of mandate to carry out OA-related activities. Many librarians see tremendous benefits in moving towards OA. Not only might OA reduce the pressure on library budgets, it could also provide more resources faster for users by supplementing paid resources with ones that are freely available, mitigate costs for resource purchase and access, as well as reduce the complexities involved in negotiating electronic journal and database licenses (Harris, 2012; Morrison, 2006; Palmer, Dill & Christie, 2009).

Special programmes have also been put in place to offer greater access to researchers in institutions that cannot afford traditional journal subscriptions, including institutions in certain countries within the ERA. Research4Life²⁰ is a public-private partnership of the WHO; Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO); United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP); World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO); Cornell and Yale Universities; the International Association of Scientific, Technical & Medical Publishers; and Microsoft. Intended to facilitate the flow of knowledge from more developed countries to developing countries, it is subdivided into four separate programmes, each addressing the needs of researchers in specific disciplines: HINARI (Health InterNetwork Access to Research Initiative); AGORA (Access to Global Online Research in Agriculture); OARE (Online Access to Research in Environment); and ARDI (Access to Research for Development and Innovation). Other programmes include the Essential Electronic Agricultural Library (TEEAL) and the Scientific Electronic Library Online (SciELO).

²⁰ Research4life. (2014). *Programmes* [Web page]. www.research4life.org/about/

3 Policies on open data—free access to scientific data

This section presents information on the OA concept applied to data more generally with a particular emphasis on scientific data. Section 3.1 presents national policies and initiatives related to open data (OD). Funders' policies promoting OD are presented in Section 3.2 and the various strategies adopted by research institutions to support OD follow in Section 3.3. Section 3.4 presents publishers' responses to OA. Finally, the challenges in the development of open data are presented in Section 3.5.

3.1 National policies and initiatives

Governments generate substantial amounts of data, most often in the form of statistics and raw data collected through censuses, geographical surveys, public spending oversight and other large scale monitoring activities. These activities result in large datasets that are funded, produced and owned by governments. These data cannot strictly be considered 'scientific,' as they are not generated through scientific research, but they are commonly used by scientists and social scientists. To date, most national open data policies target these types of datasets rather than scientific data at large.

Although comprehensive open access policies may not be on the immediate agenda of governments, their importance was recognised in 2004 by the Ministers of Science and Technology of the then 30 Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) countries, as well as China, Israel, Russia and South Africa. The Ministers asked the OECD to develop a set of principles and guidelines, which were published in 2007, to facilitate cost-effective access to digital research data from public funding. The OECD's guidelines define openness as "access on equal terms for the international research community at the lowest possible cost, preferably at no more than the marginal cost of dissemination" (OECD, 2007). The guidelines further state that OA to research data from public funding should be easy, timely, user-friendly and preferably distributed through the internet, where the marginal costs of transmitting data are close to zero.

Governments will benefit from open data not only because it can lead to more efficient and effective government, but because it can facilitate innovation and economic growth, more transparency and accountability, the greater inclusiveness of citizens and democratic participation, and strengthened law enforcement (Davies, 2013; Huijboom & Van den Broek, 2011). For governments, the OECD noted that access to research data "increases the returns from public investment in this area; reinforces open scientific inquiry; encourages diversity of studies and opinion; promotes new areas of work and enables the exploration of topics not envisioned by the initial investigators" (OECD, 2007).

For example, some of the greatest potential benefits to creating open access to scientific data include economic growth and job creation deriving from innovation, as suggested in the 2006 MEPSIR study (Measuring European Public Sector Resources) and the example of the public release of Global Positioning System (GPS) technology, developed by the US Department of Defence in the 1970s. A recent study has estimated that the use of GPS technology in the commercial sector alone directly contributed \$96 billion per year to the American economy, that 3.3 million jobs relied heavily on it, and that the economic importance of the technology is expected to keep growing (Pham, 2011).

Opening up scientific data may also inform policy and further governmental research through the exchange of data generated by various agencies and ministries. The sharing of data between agencies of the same government is often limited by subscription fees or by the

development of operational silos, leading to unnecessary expenses. The development of efficient means of data diffusion within a government or between levels of government within the same country can not only help to avoid the duplication of research but generate richer data from the crossing of various datasets. It has been estimated that by unlocking the potential of big data, European developed economies could save between €150 and €300 billion annually in the form of operational efficiency gains and increased actual versus potential collection of tax revenue (Manyika, 2011).

The political and administrative agendas in a rising number of countries now include the defining of open data strategies for public research data through a range of projects, declarations and policy, including legislation. According to the Open Data Barometer project led by the Open Data Institute, over half of the 77 countries surveyed in the 2013 iteration of the Project have implemented initiatives, ranging from open data portals launched within an e-government framework to wide-scale implementations; more than 25% of these strategies are receiving senior-level political backing and dedicated resources (Davies, 2013). However, the actual availability of open data lags behind the formation and presence of related policies.

A survey by Huijboom and Van den Broek (2011) revealed that the instruments applied by countries to implement their open data strategies and policies tend to fall under the categories of: education and training, such as knowledge exchange platforms, guidelines and conferences; voluntary approaches, such as strategies, programmes and recommendations; economic instruments, such as competitions and financing of open data portals; and legislation and control, such as public sector information laws, Freedom of Information acts, technical standards and monitoring.

Surveys and scans that examine the global spread of open data strategies and open datasets, such as the aforementioned Open Data Barometer project and the Open Data Census by the Open Knowledge Foundation²¹, have found that the countries with the greatest numbers of both are the UK, the US, Denmark, Norway, the Netherlands and Sweden. Below are some of the more notable recent developments in the countries that have placed a high policy priority on open data, as well as some significant developments on an international scale.

United States: In the United States, strides have been made in recent years to implement a system of data sharing that relies on machine-readable, standardised and clearly licensed data sharing. A particularly eventful year was 2009, which saw the release of the President's Memorandum on Transparency and Open Government and the Office of Management and Budget's (OMB) Open Government Directive, as well as the launching of Data.gov, which is considered the world's first high-profile national open government data initiative.

On 9 May 2013, President Barack Obama issued an Executive Order (a decree of the President that has the full force of law) entitled Making Open and Machine Readable the New Default for Government Information. The Order, which outlined the new federal open data policy, stipulated that all newly generated government data will be required to be made available in open, machine-readable formats. The policy is also being applied to existing systems that are being modernized or upgraded. Shortly following the Order, the White House announced Project Open Data, an initiative developed to encourage federal government agencies to share and produce their open data. The accompanying policy memorandum²²

²¹ <https://index.okfn.org/country/>

²² <http://project-open-data.github.io/policy-memo/>

(Open Data Policy—Managing Information as an Asset) sets out the “collection of code, tools, and case studies” for the purpose of helping agencies adopt the policy. The Project has led to some controversy, however, due to its assertion that datasets should be ‘licensed,’ which would potentially create confusion about their public domain status.

A number of open data policies have also been enacted at the state, city and county levels; 39 US states and 46 US cities and counties have such policies, including Washington DC, New York, San Francisco, Portland and Chicago (as of April 2014).

United Kingdom: Unlike the US, the government of the United Kingdom has supported open data without having enacted major legislative change. An Open Government Data initiative emphasizing the support of innovation and economic growth through data sharing was launched in 2009 and has since retained high level support. The next year, the Data.gov.uk project, led by the Transparency and Open Data team in the Cabinet Office, was launched in beta version. As part of the project, each government department was required to create a departmental open data strategy. Data.gov.uk presently houses over 9,000 datasets from all central government departments and a number of other public sector bodies and local authorities.

In 2012, the Open Data Institute was launched with support from the UK government with the goal of “catalysing the evolution of open data culture to create economic, environmental, and social value.”²³ Also that year, an Open Data White Paper entitled “Unleashing the Potential” was submitted by the Minister for the Cabinet Office and Paymaster (UK Cabinet Office, 2012). The paper sets out “how the UK will continue to unlock and seize the benefits of data sharing in the future in a responsible way” in terms of easing access to public data; better enabling data publishers to release data in standardised, open formats; and engraining a ‘presumption to publish’ unless there are clear reasons not to do so. At the local level, as well, authorities operate under mandates to publish certain open datasets, with many having established their own data portals.

Sweden: Sweden was the first country in the world to enact a Right to Information law in 1776, which was updated in 2003. In 2012, the country instituted its own data portal as a pilot. This was followed two years later by the open data portal of the Riksdag, Sweden’s national legislative assembly, which is managed by the Vinnova, the National Innovation Agency.

Denmark: Denmark’s government enacted law no. 596 in 2005. The legislation covers the re-use of public sector data and establishes the implementation of the EU Public Sector Information (PSI) directive. In July 2010, the country’s Open Data Innovation Strategy was launched by the Danish Ministry of Science, Technology and Innovation. One of the Strategy’s key pillars is to create (open) technical standards that stimulate interoperability (Davies, 2013; Huijboom & Van den Broek, 2011).

European Union: Within the European Union, the PSI Directive (2003/98/EC) on the re-use of public sector information is the main legal instrument applicable across the 28 EU Member States. A revised Directive was issued in June 2013. Another key open data policy tool is Regulation (EC) no. 1049/2001, which governs access to documents held by three major institutions: Parliament, Council and Commission. It, too, is currently being revised in order to bring all the EU institutions, bodies, offices and agencies within its scope. For research funded

²³ <http://theodi.org/>

by EU funding programmes, resulting scientific publications in selected areas are to be made openly accessible after an embargo period, supported by an electronic infrastructure using existing OA repositories in the Member States. In Horizon 2020, the policy will apply to research in all areas. In December 2012, the EU Open Data Portal was launched. The Portal, which provides access to Commission data, as well as those of other EU institutions and bodies, was based on the Commission Decision that issued rules on the re-use of Commission documents and the Communication on Open Data: An engine for innovation, growth and transparent governance, both from December 2011 (European Commission, 2013).

In June of 2013, leaders of the G8 countries (the US, the UK, Canada, Russia, France, Germany, Italy and Japan) signed and adopted the Open Data Charter, which sets out the five strategic principles that all G8 members must act on in the implementation of open data policies. The first principle is that of ‘open by default,’ also espoused in the 2013 Executive Order issued by President Obama. The remaining four principles state that the data must increase in quality and quantity, be usable by all, and be released and used for the purposes of improved governance and for the purposes of innovation. The Open Data Charter is considered by many to be unmistakable evidence of the growing importance of open data.

3.1.1 National infrastructure

A number of governments are already developing the infrastructure required to collect, manage and disseminate scientific data. As with national open data policies, the focus of these efforts has been government rather than scientific data. The bulk of currently available open governmental data repositories belong to smaller governmental entities, such as states, provinces and municipalities. A few national repositories now offer access to staggering amounts of data. As the acceptability and economic benefits of open data grow, more countries can be expected to develop similar infrastructure.

The US government was the first to establish its own open data portal, data.gov, in 2009. At its onset, the repository contained only 47 datasets. As of April 2014, this number has grown to more than 95,000 datasets, including raw datasets, tools and geodata. Not all data accessible through these portals are truly OA, as access fees or restrictions may apply to certain datasets. For example, Germany’s public service information portal, govdata.de, uses a custom licence model which may preclude re-use of the data, especially in combination with other datasets.

International organisations that have launched open data portals include the United Nations’ portal, data.un.org; the OECD’s portal, OECDiLibrary; the World Bank’s repository, data.worldbank.org; and the European Commission’s portal, open-data.europa.eu.

3.2 Funders’ policies and initiatives

Policies that address open scientific data are more common at the level of funding bodies and research institutions than in government agencies. In general, funding bodies do not directly produce scientific data, but they may have an interest in archiving and disseminating data generated by their grantees. In doing so, funders may better monitor the outcomes of their investments, increase the visibility of their contribution to research and ensure long-term preservation of the data. If they have the means to mine and further analyse the data collected from multiple projects, funders may also use this information to highlight underrepresented or emerging areas of interest and adapt their policies accordingly.

Funding bodies have far fewer OA policies for scientific data than policies for scientific publications. This may be due to technical challenges in the implementation of suitable

infrastructure and standards to manage the data. Funders may also perceive fewer advantages stemming from OA data than from OA peer-reviewed publications in terms of their visibility. In an analysis conducted by Science-Metrix of 48 funders' OA policies listed in ROARMAP within ERA countries, Brazil, Canada and the US, 23% explicitly excluded data from OA requirements and 38% did not mention data at all. Conversely, 29% of policies mandated open data archiving and 10% encouraged it without mandating it.

Although they are still in the minority, funding agencies that expect applicants to create and adhere to data storage, access and management plans are increasing in number, with many agencies attaching conditions that strongly encourage or require the sharing of data with as few restrictions as possible and within a specified time frame. Prominent examples of data sharing policies that include OA mandates include the following:

- In the US, well-known data policies include those of the National Institutes of Health (NIH) and the American Heart Association (AHA). For instance, applicants for AHA grants are required to submit a data sharing plan, and research data must be made freely available within 12 months of the end of the funding period. The American Psychological Association (APA) also provides grantees with a list of approved data repositories.
- In the UK, the Common Principles on Data Policy of the Research Councils UK (RCUK) upholds data sharing among grant holders. For example, the Economic and Social Research Council (ESRC) requires grantees to make their data available for re-use, even attaching financial penalties to non-compliance; the only exceptions are those with compelling reasons not to share data. Additionally, applicants must include a statement on data sharing and fill out a section that requires them to propose a strategy for the collection of new data. The Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council (EPSRC) announced its Policy Framework on Research Data in 2011. Those institutions that receive EPSRC research contracts have been asked to develop data sharing roadmaps that align with the EPSRC's directives, with full compliance expected by 1 May 2015.

For funding bodies, OA databases for scientific data are a relatively new concern. Although most recommend the use of institutional, disciplinary or aggregating repositories, some funding bodies operate their own repositories. Funding bodies that require data archiving in their own repositories fall into two categories:

- Large organisations with a clear disciplinary profile that involves generating a critical mass of data to attract users; and
- Smaller organisations that use their data repositories mostly for verification and transparency purposes.

Perhaps the most notable OA scientific databases include the NIH's GenBank, the DNA DataBank of Japan (DDBJ) and the European Molecular Biology Laboratory (EMBL) Nucleotide Sequence Database (funded by public research funds from 20 member countries). These databases are directly linked and seamlessly and constantly share data.

3.3 Research institutions' strategies for OA to scientific data

While universities lack a champion for the cause of open data, at least compared to the advocacy of OA to scholarly publications, they are increasingly taking notice of developments at the government and funding agency levels and reviewing their own procedures related to research data sharing practices. Many are developing research data management policies that cover data preservation and sharing (Mauthner, 2013). Examples of universities that have implemented such policies include Oxford University in the UK and Yale University in the US.

In a survey of head librarians at universities and higher learning institutions conducted by Science-Metrix, 73% of respondents agreed or strongly agreed that providing scholarly publications in OA form is a priority in their organisation, whereas only 45% agreed or strongly agreed that providing scientific data in OA form is a priority. A similar trend is observed in the adoption of OA policies for scholarly publications and scientific data. Only 11% of respondents to the survey indicated that their institution has an OA policy for scientific data, while for scholarly publications, 42% indicated that their institution has an OA policy. Thus, establishing institutional frameworks for the diffusion of data in OA remains a secondary concern at this point.

3.3.1 Infrastructure developed by research institutions

Only a handful of institutional repositories are dedicated to research data; it is more common for institutions to support datasets on repositories otherwise devoted to books, theses, peer-reviewed publications and multimedia objects. In the survey of head librarians at universities and higher learning institutions conducted by Science-Metrix, 36% of respondents indicated that their organisation maintains one or more repositories for open access scientific data, whereas 11% of respondents indicated that their organisation had a policy to this effect. Thus, the infrastructure required to host and share scientific data, while still uncommon, seems more developed than the associated policy frameworks.

For the countries covered in this study, as of April 2014, ROAR lists 21 repositories for “research data” and *OpenDOAR* lists 112 repositories that support the deposit of “datasets.” *OpenDOAR* is the most comprehensive directory of OA repositories, but organisations must register for their repositories to be listed. It is therefore by no means exhaustive, and the repositories listed could merely be the tip of the iceberg.

Open scientific data has the potential to strengthen the credibility of scholarly publications because it opens the process of peer-review to the entire scientific community. In the current system, a publication’s validity is judged by a handful of people outside of the research team, and the discovery of mistakes or fraud after publication is unlikely unless subsequent studies attempt to duplicate the results. Cases of retractions and flawed studies, whether the flaws are due to error or scientific misconduct, should be a major argument in favour of open access to scientific data as a complement to traditional peer review. Easily accessible data would extend the peer review process beyond a small group of reviewers acting before publication to all readers after publication.

3.4 Publishers’ responses to open data

Whereas scholarly journal publishers often considered OA publications to be a threat to their traditional markets, the legal and economic implications of OA to scientific data are far fewer for publishers than in the case of scholarly publications. In fact, the Association of Learned and Professional Society Publishers (ALPSP) and the International Association of Scientific, Technical & Medical Publishers (STM) declared in a joint statement that “as a general principle, data sets [...] should wherever possible be made freely accessible to other scholars. We believe that the best practice for scholarly journal publishers is to separate supporting data from the article itself, and not to require any transfer of or ownership in such data or data sets as a condition of publication of the article in question” (ALPSP and STM, 2006).

A number of scientific journals are implementing data archiving policies that require that any supporting datasets for the articles that they publish be made publicly available as a condition of publication. The benefits of such journal publisher mandates may be significant.

A study by Vines et al. (2013) found that journal-based data archiving policies effectively ensure that research data are made available to the scientific community, especially when journals require that a data accessibility statement appear in the manuscript.

3.5 Challenges in the development of open data

Compared to OA repositories of theses and scientific articles, institutional repositories that support the archiving of scientific datasets remain marginal. Challenges include the costs associated with setting up and maintaining repositories and databases, such as those related to storage, security and quality-control procedures and standardisation (Wilhelm, Oster & Shoulson, 2014). The heterogeneous nature of scientific data is an additional challenge, particularly difficulties associated with the standardisation of data and metadata formats, poor indexation by internet browsers, and the scarcity of directories or registries that could make data more visible. Several disciplinary standards have been developed to index specific types of records in the face of an ever-rising tide of data. Although the development of some of these standards predates widespread internet access, all have evolved to adapt to it, and most use XML, which is readable by machines and humans alike. The preservation of data and the confidentiality of data are a concern with respect to the dissemination of data generated by studies of human subjects.

Additional barriers to the widespread implementation of open access to data have been identified. These include a closed government culture; privacy legislation, absence of strong Right to Information laws, or weak or absent data protection laws; limited quality of data, limited user-friendliness of data; unequal access to data; lack of standardisation of policy; security threats; existing charging models; lack of awareness, education and public interest; and uncertain economic impacts (Davies, 2013; Fioretti, 2014; Huijboom & Van den Broek, 2011).

4 Estimating the proportion of open access publications

This study assesses OA availability during the 1996–2013 period by carefully tuning harvesting methods in order to substantially increase recall (recall is the capacity to harvest all relevant items). A deep dive was also performed for the last six years to cross-tabulate the data in 22 scientific fields with the proportion of OA papers in the European Research Area (ERA) and in selected countries. Some 1.25 million papers were sampled to carry out the present study, making it, to the best of our knowledge, the largest-scale study undertaken to date on this subject. A prelude to the present study included an important pilot phase as well as a first phase of large-scale measurement (sample size of 320,000 records), the results of which were presented in an earlier version of the present report (Archambault et al. 2013).

The harvesting engine developed by Science-Metrix searches on a large number of specific sites, including SciELO, PubMed Central and the websites of scientific peer-reviewed journal publishers; uses a locally hosted version of large-scale specialised repositories such as arXiv; and systematically harvests metadata from institutional repositories listed in ROAR and *OpenDOAR*, in addition to having a portion of the harvesting engine working in the cloud and searching for freely available papers.

Before entering into the methodological details associated with the measurement of freely accessible papers, it is important to produce operational definitions of Green, Gold and other types of freely accessible papers (see the introduction for more complete and also somewhat more theoretical definitions).

Operational definitions of open access

In the present report, the following operational definitions were used to perform measurement:

Green OA: refers to papers which are self-archived by authors and available on institutional repositories as listed in *OpenDOAR*²⁴ and/or ROAR.²⁵ Listings in *OpenDOAR* and ROAR which correspond to known Gold OA Journals were set aside. Aggregator sites such as CiteSeerX were not considered here, since, even though they access article submissions, they do not constitute a repository in the classical sense. Likewise, articles in the main PubMed Central sites were not counted as Green as they have curtailed usage rights or limited download rights.²⁶ Because it is commonly difficult to determine whether a paper was self-archived before, at the same time as or after publication and also how long it will be available on the internet, Green OA includes Green OA, Delayed Green and Transient Green. Note that some of these articles may not respect restrictions placed by journal publishers (many of whose rules can be found on SHERPA/RoMEO)²⁷ and therefore contain a certain number of Robin Hood OA papers. Finally, only articles which could be downloaded without user registrations were considered.

²⁴ <http://www.opendoar.org/>

²⁵ <http://roar.eprints.org/>

²⁶ The PubMed Central site mentions “You may NOT use any kind of automated process to download articles in bulk from the main PMC site. PMC will block the access of any user who is found to be violating this policy.” See <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/about/faq/#q12>

²⁷ <http://www.sherpa.ac.uk/romeo/>

Gold Journal OA: refers to papers appearing in journals listed in the DOAJ²⁸ and on the PubMed Central list of journals.²⁹ When a paper is published during the first year that a journal appears in the DOAJ, it is not counted. This is a conservative decision due to the fact that one cannot determine whether a journal started publishing Gold articles early or late during the year. For PubMed Central, only open access journals with full participation and immediate access were considered to be Gold, hence all journals with an embargo and in the ‘NIH Portfolio’ were not considered. Thus, this category covers articles appearing in Gold journals and excludes delayed Gold as well as piecemeal Gold (Gold articles in paid access journals, also called hybrid OA).

Other OA: refers to more or less everything that could be found on the web by a determined researcher and downloaded for free and which is not part of the Green and Gold operational definitions above. This comprises articles appearing in journals with an embargo period (Delayed Gold OA); articles appearing on authors’ webpages and elsewhere (both Green OA and Rogue OA); articles appearing on aggregator sites such as ResearchGate and CiteSeerX in addition to PubMed Central. The category comprises both transiently and permanently accessible items as there are no reliable ways to ascertain at measurement time whether an item will be permanently accessible or not.

Total OA: The mutually exclusive sum of Green OA, Gold Journal OA and Other OA.

4.1 Methods

This section presents the key metrology concepts used in this study (Section 4.1.1) and a detailed characterisation of the accuracy of the measurement techniques used for the present study (Section 4.1.2). This report covers the largest and final measurement phase (Section 4.1.3).

4.1.1 Key OA metrology concepts

This report presents results using two important metrology concepts (JCGM, 2008): (1) *trueness*, which reflects the quality of the instruments used and the care taken in making measurements; and (2) *precision*, which reflects the use of repeated measures, sampling and statistical analysis (see Figure 2). The latter concept will be called *statistical precision* to distinguish the need to use multiple measures in order to reduce the margin of error from the different tasks involved in performing binary classification work is to determine whether a document belongs to a category (e.g. OA or Non-OA).

²⁸ <https://doaj.org/about>

²⁹ <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/journals/>

Figure 2 **Trueness and statistical precision**Source: Adapted from http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Accuracy_and_precision.

Statistical precision can be assessed with the margin of error (ME). For a proportion (p) where the population is finite and known (which is the case here as the population from which we are sampling is the Scopus database), (N) is not systematically much larger than the sample size (n), and in which the values are discrete (for example, papers are discrete as one does not publish one third of a paper), given a critical score Z (which will be set at 0.95 in the study), ME is calculated as follows:

$$ME = Z \sqrt{\frac{p(1-p)(N-n)}{n(N-1)} + \frac{0.5}{n}}$$

What complicates the use of these definitions is the need to examine how true our measures are using two more concepts used in information retrieval: recall and precision (as opposed to the first concept of ‘statistical precision’; the second precision-related concept will be referred to as ‘retrieval precision’).

Recall is the proportion of relevant records that are retrieved (capacity to avoid having false negatives or of not making type II errors), while retrieval precision is the proportion of retrieved records that are relevant (capacity to avoid including false positives or of not making type I errors). In a way, low recall might be seen as undershooting a target, while low precision could be seen as overshooting. Recall is frequently an easy-to-reach design goal, as it can be achieved by just selecting everything. However, a good measurement instrument has to avoid including items that are not relevant (that is, including false positives) and to balance recall with precision, since increasing recall usually comes at the cost of lowering precision.

If an instrument retrieves 25 records of which only 20 are relevant, and fails to retrieve 30 additional relevant records, its retrieval precision is $20/25 = 80\%$, and its recall $25/50 = 50\%$. Thus, high recall means that an instrument returned most of the relevant results, while high retrieval precision means that it retrieved more relevant results than irrelevant ones.

Overall, in order to perform an accurate estimate of the proportion of OA in a population of papers published in peer-reviewed journals, one needs to (1) keep the statistical level of error low (high statistical precision) by having a large sample size; (2) have a high level of recall in order to avoid missing relevant records (thereby underestimating the real population); and (3) have a high level of retrieval precision to avoid including spurious records (thereby overestimating the real population).

4.1.2 Characterisation of the measurement apparatus

The results from a perfect classifier would solely comprise a mix of true positives and true negatives. A true positive (tp) in the present case is a paper known to be available in OA which is found by the harvesting instrument developed for the current project. A true negative (tn) is an article which is not available for free and is not found by the instrument. However, such an instrument rarely is perfect and there are usually false positives (fp), that is, articles not available for free but wrongly assigned to this category, and false negatives (fn), that is, articles available for free but that are not found by the instrument. These concepts can be used to characterise how good measurement is in terms of retrieval precision and recall.

Retrieval precision, also called positive predictive value, provides an estimation of how frequently the instrument finds correct positive results and is calculated as follows:

$$\text{Retrieval Precision} = \frac{tp}{tp+fp}$$

Recall, also called true positive rate or sensitivity, is the capacity to correctly identify a large proportion of the positive records:

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{tp}{tp+fn}$$

Knowing the precise characteristics in terms of true and false positives and negatives allows for the computation of an adjustment score, which can then applied to recalibrate the results to obtain a truer measure, one that corrects the limits of the instrument. The adjustment made in the previous study is based on the following formula:

$$\text{Adjustment} = \frac{tp+fn}{tp+fp}$$

The same sample of 500 articles previously used in a pilot study was also used for the characterisation of the OA harvester used to measure availability of the million papers and the close to a quarter million samples of papers used for the present study. Whereas 238 articles were available for free in December 2012 (47.6%), 224 articles could be found in April 2013 (44.8%) and 243 in April 2014 (48.6%). It is also noteworthy that 272 articles were available for free at one time or another between December 2012 and April 2013, that is 54.4%. Between December 2012 and April 2013, 11 new records appeared in OA, but 25 disappeared, a large part of the latter (13 out of 25) actually being Springer articles available for free during the limited time of a promotion. Most of the others were on websites that disappeared, or they no longer appeared on the website where they were originally found. A further 10 papers that could be found in April 2013 had disappeared by April 2014 (or could only be found because we had the old link since neither Google, Google Scholar, or our own harvester could find them). That is, a total of 35 papers that could be found either in December 2012 or in April 2013 disappeared afterwards (7% of the sample). These results suggest that there are important transient aspects that need to be taken into consideration when measuring OA availability. Free articles sometimes come and go and it is therefore important to present information not only on the year of publication of articles, but also when the measure was actually made. This also makes replication of results a challenging undertaking.

The characterisation of the harvester reveals that this measurement instrument has excellent retrieval precision (99.1%) and fairly good recall (86.4%). Our design goal is to maximize retrieval precision at the expense of recall, and progressively improve recall while maintaining or improving precision. We therefore consider the harvesting engine's results as consistent with these goals and sufficiently good to present robust measures of OA availability. Please note that even the method used here is a floor of OA availability as neither Google nor Google Scholar, which were used to determine the 'ground truth,' can be expected to have perfect recall scores.

Because our harvester tends overall to underestimate the availability of OA, an adjustment factor of 1.146 was used in some graphs and tables for Total OA (this adjustment cannot be used for Green OA, Gold OA, or Other OA, which would need their own calibration). When in use, this calibrated measure is always indicated as 'adjusted OA.' In the absence of the adjusted measure, the statistics should be considered to be floor values providing a conservative estimate of the OA proportion.

Table I OA availability in April 2014 of a sample of 500 articles published in 2008

Type of results	Articles	Characteristics	Score
True positive (tp)	210	Retrieval precision	99.1%
True negative (tn)	255	Recall	86.4%
False positive (fp)	2	Adjustment factor	1.146
False negative (fn)	33	ME of the Adjustment	4.5%

Source: Computed by Science-Metrix using Scopus, DOAJ and numerous sources of freely downloadable papers.

The following limits to the calibration should be noted: the 500-record sample size used to calibrate the score is relatively small and increasing that sample size would increase the reliability of the adjustment. For a confidence interval of 95%, the margin of error for a proportion of 50% is 4.5 percentage points. Only records from 2008 were calibrated, which might create some imperfection in randomness as these records may have different characteristics from records of other years. The adjustment was computed only for overall OA; separate calibrations for Green OA, Gold OA and Other OA would also be desirable.

Please note that in the tables, the values are presented as percentages and the errors in percentage points, that is, 50 ± 2 means that the proportion could be as low as 48% and as high as 52%. When presenting data with Adjusted scores, the margin of error was obtained using the following Pythagorean formula where ME_{tot} is the margin of error, ME_s is the margin of error due to the actual sample size used for the measurement of the OA proportion and ME_a is the margin of error due to the sample size used for the calibration of the harvesting instrument:

$$ME_{tot} = \sqrt{ME_s^2 + ME_a^2}$$

4.1.3 Strategy to measure the proportion of Green, Gold and Other OA

Two random samples were created for this last phase of the study. The first one spanned the 1996 to 2013 period. Articles were randomly selected from Scopus until the year with the fewest papers had 10,000 papers; this year happened to be 1996, as expected, as it had the fewest records. The target of 10,000 papers was computed on the basis that it would yield a statistical margin of error of 1%, which we had arbitrarily selected. This sample, comprising metadata for more than 245,000 papers, was used to study the overall proportion of Green OA, Gold Journal OA, Other OA and Total OA at the world level.

A second sample comprising one million records was drawn to perform detailed measurements for the relatively recent past, that is, the 2008 to 2013 period. More specifically, this sample was used to cross-tabulate 22 scientific domains with all the countries in the ERA. Additional articles were retrieved for smaller fields, but these were only used to compute statistics at the field level.

The determination of whether a paper in the sample was available in Green or Other OA form involved the use of a custom-built harvester. The harvesting engine developed by Science-Metrix searches specific sites, including SciELO, PubMed Central, Research Gate and CiteSeerX, and the websites of scientific, peer-reviewed journal publishers. It uses a locally hosted version of large-scale specialised repositories such as arXiv and systematically harvests metadata from institutional repositories listed in ROAR and *OpenDOAR*; in addition, a portion of the harvesting engine works in the cloud and searches for freely available papers.

For Gold Journal OA articles, an estimate of the proportion of papers was made from the random sample by matching the journals that were known to be Gold to the year a paper was published. These journals were obtained from the DOAJ and the list of OA journals in PubMed Central. This was done by matching journals' ISSN, E-ISSN and names from Scopus to the relevant records in the sample (the matching had close to 100% precision, but recall may have been imperfect, hence the figures presented here can be considered to be a floor, rather than a ceiling).

4.2 OA availability and impact of papers published between 1996 and 2013

This section examines the evolution of the proportion of papers published between 1996 and 2013 which can be downloaded for free as of April 2014 (Section 4.2.1) followed by the different types of OA: Green OA (Section 4.2.2), papers published in Gold OA journals (Section 4.2.3) and papers published in other types of OA (Section 4.2.4). Section 4.2.5 examines the contribution of each type of OA to the overall availability of freely downloadable papers. Finally, Section 4.2.6 examines the evolution of the impact of OA and non-OA papers.

4.2.1 Growth of OA

Measuring the growth of OA was one of the central aspects of this research project. It is considerably difficult to measure the growth of OA compared to the majority of growth phenomena. The reason is that growth in OA appears as the result of four main forces: (1) historical growth in the interest in OA, which translates into *new papers* being increasingly available for free; (2) the growing interest in OA, which translates into actors increasingly making available *old papers* for free; (3) OA policies that allow for delaying OA to scientific papers with embargo periods, which produce a concomitant disembargoing of scientific articles that creates additional growth in old papers being made available for free; and (4) the fact that the number of published scientific papers is growing, which means that even for a stable proportion of OA, the number of OA papers would keep growing.

Whereas growth of new items typically creates geometric patterns such as exponential and logistic growth curves, backfilling creates an upward movement of the curve presenting the proportion of freely available papers, which is called a translation movement in mathematics. Embargoes makes measurement more complex as the growth curves experience a levelling off and a fall as one gets closer to the present day. As mentioned, the number of scientific papers is itself increasing over time—6.6% growth per year can be observed in Scopus between 2003 and 2012. Again, this means that even in the absence of growth in OA availability, one could actually see an increase in the *number of papers* available in OA.

These concepts can be seen clearly in Figure 3. The figure presents the results of the latest measurement phase based on 245,000 records randomly selected between 1996 and 2013, in addition to the previous round of measurement performed in April 2013 on the 2004 to 2011 period. Adjusted scores are based on the careful characterisation of the harvesting engine presented in Section 4.1.2 (Table I) and take into account the retrieval precision and recall of the OA harvester used for this study. The curves illustrate growth over time, the translation of the curves that appear in a period of one year, and the effect of embargoes and Delayed OA.

Figure 3 Evolution of the proportion of OA scientific papers as measured in April 2013 and April 2014, 1996–2013

Source: Computed by Science-Metrix using Scopus, DOAJ and numerous sources of freely downloadable papers.

Figure 4 shows the difference in the curve as measured in April 2013 and in April of the current year (2014) to see the type of change that occurred in the availability of OA over one year. There are interesting observations to be made from the adjusted OA curves. Firstly, if one does not take the translation movement into account, the overall growth of OA appears to be quite slow. The curve obtained last year suggested that OA was growing at a rate of 1.9% per year. Interestingly, the curve obtained this year shows an acceleration of OA availability, since the growth rate is now 2.4%, an increase in growth of 0.5%. The translation is therefore not a perfect parallel movement as the curves diverge going forward. As measured in 2004, there is a 3.6 percentage point gap between the two curves, and this gap is 6 percentage points wide in 2011.

Figure 4 Translation of OA availability between April 2013 and April 2014

Source: Computed by Science-Metrix using Scopus, DOAJ and numerous sources of freely downloadable papers.

These estimates were used to produce an estimate of the backfilling of old papers published between 1996 and 2011 that were made available for free during the year separating the measures made in April 2013 and those made in April 2014. According to this model, close to

14,000 papers published in 1996 were made available for free during the last year, and nearly 100,000 papers published in 2011. Backfilling is truly important to understand how OA grows: a total of 700,000 papers published between 1996 and 2011, as indexed in Scopus, were made available for free between April 2013 and April 2014. Considering that there are about 18 million papers in Scopus for this period, this represents an increase in availability of 3.9 percentage points.

The combination of all the trends, including the growth in scientific papers published every year, yields the curves (as measured and as adjusted for the instrument's shortcomings) presented in Figure 5. As of April 2014, the number of available papers increases by 9.4% per year. Of the papers published in 1996, 240,000 papers are now available for free, as are 950,000 of the papers published in 2012. Based on the adjusted OA availability statistics, one can estimate that about 47% of the papers indexed in Scopus between 1996 and 2013 can be downloaded for free as of April 2014. This means that 10.1 million papers would be downloadable out of the 21.5 million papers indexed in Scopus for that period that can be considered to be peer-reviewed papers published in scientific journals. The results presented here clearly show that understanding the growth of OA availability cannot be undertaken without references to simultaneously occurring phenomena such as growth in OA interest, backfilling, disembargoing and the growth in scientific papers publishing.

Figure 5 Growth of the number of papers available in OA as measured in April 2014, 1996–2013

Source: Computed by Science-Metrix using Scopus, DOAJ and numerous sources of freely downloadable papers.

4.2.2 Green OA as a proportion of scientific papers

Green OA is the most difficult aspect of OA to measure. Advocates of OA such as Stevan Harnad insist that Green OA should only include immediately available OA, i.e., it should exclude DOA Green (Delayed OA). This creates considerable problems from a measurement point of view as, for each paper, one would need to have in hand both the official date of publication (the definition of which is itself open to discussion) and the date when a paper is placed in a repository. As mentioned by Björk, Laakso, Welling & Paetau (2014), “[t]ypically, Green OA copies become available with considerable time delays, partly caused by publisher imposed embargo periods, and partly by author tendencies to archive manuscripts only periodically.”

The definition also mentions that Green OA is self-archiving by authors and given the increasingly complex set of mandates being promulgated by numerous parties in the promotion of OA, it is sometimes difficult to determine whether it was the author or the publisher who archived the paper. Because of this, in part, repositories such as PubMed Central were not considered here. The focus on Green OA measurement is therefore the repositories listed in ROAR and *OpenDOAR* (see also Sections 1 and 2 on the methodological aspects). Also note that last year’s measurement did not provide an estimate of Green OA and it is therefore not possible to examine changes that have occurred since. The evolution of Green OA, as defined operationally here, is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6 Growth of the proportion and number of Green OA papers as measured in April 2014, 1996–2013

Source: Computed by Science-Metrix using Scopus as well as ROAR, *OpenDOAR* and institutional repositories.

While the number of papers has grown steadily, this appears to be due to the background growth, that is, the growth in published scientific papers. Green OA as a percentage of the papers indexed in Scopus appears to have levelled off from around 2004. This requires further investigation to determine whether this is a measurement artefact—an effect of the imperfect operational definition of Green OA used here—or if Green OA is somewhat losing steam. Despite this, about 1.2 million papers were available in Green OA form in repositories across the world, and the growth rate of OA papers was 8.8% between 1997 and 2011.

4.2.3 Papers in Gold OA journals as a proportion of scientific papers

Figure 7 presents trends on the availability of articles published in Gold OA journals indexed in Scopus from 1996 to 2013. The percentage of articles published in Gold OA journals indexed in Scopus for 1996 was only 0.9% but grew to 12.8% for 2012, the annual growth rate being 18% for this period, which means that the proportion of articles in Gold OA journals doubles every 4.1 years. Scopus covers less than half of the journals listed in the DOAJ, so this figure likely underestimates the true contribution of Gold OA journals.

Furthermore, Gold OA papers indexed in Scopus grew exponentially up until 2012. The growth rate was 24% per year from 1996 to 2012, which means that the number of papers published in Gold OA journals doubles every 3.2 years. A decrease is observed for 2013, which cannot be readily explained. One hypothesis is that the number of Gold OA journals

indexed by the Scopus database dropped or that these articles took longer than the average article to be indexed by Elsevier. At the moment, about 1,380,000 papers from Gold journals are indexed in Scopus for 1996 to 2013.³⁰ This represents only 200,000 papers more than those available in Green OA form, but Gold OA journal papers are growing with a clear momentum, which is not so clearly the case with Green OA.

Figure 7 Growth of the proportion and number of papers published in Gold OA journals as measured in April 2014, 1996–2013

Source: Computed by Science-Metrix using Scopus as well as DOAJ and PubMedCentral.

4.2.4 Other OA as a proportion of scientific papers

As one can see in Figure 8, the evolution of Other OA is somewhat similar to that of Green OA. In terms of percentage, it increases substantially from 1996 until about 2003, at which time it levels off until 2008, when there is an observed decline in the proportion of Other OA papers. It is not a simple matter to determine what creates this shape due to the heterogeneity of the underlying dataset. These data include papers in repositories such as Pub Med Central and CiteSeerX, papers with article processing charges (so-called hybrid journals), Robin Hood or Rogue OA papers and papers stemming from journals with embargo periods. What seems to be obvious here is that unless we are witnessing a slowdown in OA development, the embargoing and other form of DOA (Delayed OA) is having a very tangible effect on the availability of scientific knowledge. This creates a situation whereby a substantial part of the material openly available is relatively old, or possibly, out-dated.

As in the case of Green OA, the growth as measured in number of papers is greater than the growth of the proportion. There was a regular increase of 8.4% per year in the number of papers from 1996 to 2009, after which the increase slowed down and dropped in 2013 as the full effect of embargos surpassed the growth in available papers (which is 6.6% per year in Scopus between 2003 and 2012).

³⁰ Since Scopus data are incomplete for 2013, a correction coefficient was applied based on an exponential regression of the number of publications (excluding those from conference proceedings) in Scopus between 1996 and 2013.

Figure 8 Growth of the proportion and number of Other OA papers as measured in April 2014, 1996–2013

Source: Computed by Science-Metrix using Scopus and numerous sources of freely downloadable papers.

4.2.5 Types of OA and total OA as a proportion of scientific papers

The results for the three types of OA measured here are presented in Figure 9. Starting from the bottom, one can find the availability of papers published in Gold OA journals. Though this was initially the lowest contributor to OA, papers in Gold OA journals are now more numerous than Green OA papers. Moreover, as one can see in the figure, the growth from Gold OA journals is what provides overall OA growth with its capacity to keep climbing. In fact, if only Green OA and other types of OA papers were considered, the increase in OA availability would be more or less flat from 2003/2004.

Green OA papers, those deposited in institutional repositories, do not contribute a large share of the overall OA stock of papers. As seen previously, their number does not increase much after 2004. A word of warning here, though: authors can also backfill repositories, and the current measurement does not take this into account as no baseline for Green OA was measured last year.

Other forms of OA—Gold OA Papers (that is, those with article processing charges published in subscription journals or so-called hybrid journals), Green DOA and Gold DOA (embargoed self-archiving and embargoed journals), ROA (Robin Hood or Rogue OA) and papers archived in non-institutional repositories such as ResearchGate—account for a large slice of the pie. This large heterogeneous set contributes the largest proportion of OA papers and there is therefore an urgent need to disaggregate this category. More research and more careful classification and thus finer-grained measures are required to better understand how these various categories contribute to OA growth, what their pattern of time-delay is, what their transiency is (especially the ROA), how important the backfilling is and how far back it goes.

One can see that we also need better measurement instruments overall as the one currently used for this study has an important gap (difference between the adjusted and the total OA) that is larger than the number of papers in Green OA that it measures and nearly as large as the number of papers published in Gold OA journals.

Still, with the tools at our disposal, we can confidently assert that, as of April 2014, more than 50% of the scientific papers published in 2007, 2008, 2009, 2010, 2011 and 2012 can be downloaded for free on the Internet. This is an important finding as only one year ago, in

April 2013, the proportion of papers that were freely available was just a hair below 50% (49.54%) in 2011 and did not reach that mark for any other year.

Figure 9 Proportion of freely available peer-reviewed papers as measured in April 2014, 1996–2013

Source: Computed by Science-Metrix using Scopus as well as DOAJ, ROAR, OpenDOAR, PubMedCentral and numerous sources of freely downloadable papers.

4.2.6 Scientific impact of OA papers

A question that has animated OA advocates has been the so-called OA citation advantage. Evidence on this question is examined in using the Average of Relative Citation (ARC), a measure that reflects citation rates and is normalised to account for differences among scientific specialities in the propensity to use references and receive citations.

On average, the citation advantage of OA papers is 40.3% while the citation disadvantage is 27% for non-OA papers (based on a total sample-size of 209,000 papers). Figure 10 reveals that OA papers were between 26% and 64% more cited on average for any given year than all papers considered, whereas non-OA received between 17% and 33% fewer citations (based on a sample size of at least 10,000 papers for any given year). Though OA papers received 64% more citations on average in 1998, the citation advantage has disappeared somewhat, probably as a result of the underlying calculations, whereby the average increasingly reflects the score of the OA papers themselves, as they constitute a growing share of the papers and a growing part of the average. The citation disadvantage of papers whose diffusion is limited to subscriptions has been quite stable.

Green OA and Other OA papers have somewhat similar patterns. Papers in subscription-based journals (non-OA articles only) and Gold OA journals are also somewhat similar to one another. On average, Green OA (operational definition used here) papers have the greatest citation advantage, being cited 53% more frequently than all papers (n=11,429). They are followed by the Other OA category, whose papers are 47% more frequently cited on average (n=64,244). Papers published in Gold OA journals have a citation disadvantage of 35% on average (n=10,913), compared with a disadvantage of 27% for non-OA papers (n=124,784).

The statistics on the impact of papers published in Gold OA journals require careful interpretation. First, many Gold journals are younger and smaller, and these factors have an

adverse effect on the citation rate and hence on measured ARC values. Authors frequently prefer reading and citing more established journals; it is therefore a challenge to start a journal from scratch and to have authors submit high-quality articles. It takes time to build a reputation and to attract established authors. Also, the ARC is not scale-invariant: larger journals have an advantage as this measure is not corrected sufficiently for journal size (namely, it is not a scale-independent measure). So it might not always be the Gold nature of journals that lowers their ‘citedness’; instead, structural aspects and imperfect measures (i.e. the scale-dependency of the ARC) might be at play. Even so, the Gold journal industry is young and it is still difficult to separate the wheat from the chaff. In this respect, it might be useful for authors to examine Beall’s List of ‘potential, possible, or probable predatory scholarly open-access publishers’ to lower one’s risk of spending money on journals that do not espouse scientific publishing best practices.³¹

Figure 10 Scientific impact of OA and non-OA papers published 1996–2011
 Source: Computed by Science-Metrix using Scopus and numerous sources of freely downloadable papers.

4.3 OA availability and impact of papers by field

This section examines the availability of OA papers (Section 4.3.1) and the advantages and disadvantages of publishing in OA papers (Section 4.3.2) by field.

4.3.1 Availability of OA papers by field

Table II presents data on the proportion of OA per field and Table III on the number of papers per field available in Green forms, in Gold journals, in Other OA and in OA overall. Considering the last three years combined (2011–2013), as of April 2014, more than 50% of the papers can be freely downloaded in 12 fields out of 22. The fields with the greatest proportion of OA are general science & technology (adjusted OA=90%), biomedical research (71%), mathematics & statistics (68%) and biology (66%). OA is not as commonly used in visual & performing arts (adjusted OA=25%), communication & textual studies (31%), historical studies (34%), engineering (35%) and philosophy & theology (35%).

³¹ <http://scholarlyoa.com/publishers/>

A growth index was computed by dividing the percentage of OA availability in 2011 and 2012 by that observed in 2008 and 2009 (2013 was left aside as embargos would distort calculated growth rates). Overall, between the two periods, there has been a 4% increase in OA availability (slightly less than 2 percentage points). The fields with the fastest growth during these periods are general science & technology, enabling & strategic technologies, public health and health services, visual & performing arts, clinical medicine, and built & environment design. Here, one can suspect that the NIH OA mandate is at play (in public health and clinical medicine).

Some of the more applied sciences, where OA was not all that prevalent in 2008, appear to be catching up, to some extent (enabling & strategic technologies, built environment & design, engineering). Growth is negative in general arts, humanities & social sciences, and slightly negative in mathematics & statistics, communication & textual studies, psychology & cognitive sciences, and economics & business.

- Green OA is particularly present in physics & astronomy (25.6%), helped by the presence of arXiv, which also plays a role in mathematics & statistics (24.3%), while economics & business is the leading field in the social sciences and humanities (11.3% of papers in Green OA).
- Gold OA availability is greatest in general science & technology (58% of the sampled papers) and lowest in general arts, humanities & social sciences (2.6%). It is also very low in visual & performing arts (2.8%), built environment & design (3.5%) and engineering (4.1%). Other fields with high availability in Gold journals include biology (17%), agriculture, fisheries & forestry (16%) and public health & health services (16%).
- Other forms of OA are frequently encountered in biomedical research (48%), psychology and cognitive sciences (43%), biology (42%), earth & environmental sciences (38%) and clinical medicine (35%).

Data in Source: Computed by Science-Metrix using Scopus as well as DOAJ, ROAR, *OpenDOAR*, PubMedCentral and numerous sources of freely downloadable papers.

Table III show that the absolute number of papers in OA form is rising rapidly (as there is also underlying growth in the number of papers generally). For example, the growth of the OA proportion in agriculture, fisheries & forestry was 1.02, but the number of papers grew at 1.16 (16% growth in the number of OA papers indexed in Scopus in 2011–2013 compared with the 2008–2009 period). Overall, out of the 4.6 million scientific papers from peer-reviewed journals indexed in Scopus during the 2011–2013 period, 2.5 million were available for free in April 2014 (adjusted OA score). A very large number of papers are freely available in clinical medicine (adjusted OA=680,000 papers), biomedical research, and physics and astronomy (close to 250,000 papers, as calculated with an adjusted measure). This is partly because of the policy of the US National Institutes of Health (NIH) mandating the use of the PubMed Central repository for supported research and because of the arXiv e-print archive, which has been largely adopted by researchers in the field of physics.

The fields where OA availability is most limited are within the social sciences and humanities and in the more applied sciences, engineering and technology. The lowest prevalence of OA availability is in visual and performing arts (adjusted OA=27%) and in communication & textual studies (31%). It is also comparatively low (less than 40% availability) in historical studies, engineering, philosophy & theology, general arts, humanities & social sciences, built environment & design, chemistry, and enabling & strategic technologies.

4.3.2 Citation advantage and disadvantage of OA papers

Source: Computed by Science-Metrix using Scopus as well as DOAJ, ROAR, *OpenDOAR*, PubMedCentral and numerous sources of freely downloadable papers.

Table IV presents data on the relative citation rate of Green OA, papers in Gold OA journals, Other OA forms and Total OA relative to all publications in each field. The ARC has been rebased at 1.0 for all fields to allow for the calculation of a citation advantage/disadvantage: this baseline comprises all the papers in a field for the given time period. A score above 1 denotes that papers are more cited than in the field overall, while a score below 1 means that these publications are less frequently cited.

All the fields derive an OA citation advantage (rebased $ARC > 1$) and, conversely, there is a sizeable citation disadvantage that goes with publishing papers that are not openly accessible one way or another. Paradoxically, many of the fields where the OA proportion is low have a sizeable citation advantage, such as the visual & performing arts (80% more cited), communication & textual studies (66%), philosophy & textual studies (63%), historical studies (55%), general arts, humanities and social sciences (51%) and engineering (38%). A likely explanation for this is that papers from researchers in these fields are more likely to be used as there are fewer OA papers available.

What is particularly interesting here is that the citation advantage is derived almost exclusively from the Green and Other OA portion, as Gold OA is associated with a citation disadvantage on average for all fields except for physics & astronomy. In earth & environment sciences and in biomedical research, there is only a fairly slight difference between Gold papers and all journals in terms of average citation rates. Currently, there is a marked disadvantage for publishing in Gold journals in general arts, humanities & social sciences, built environment & design, economics & business, and visual & performing arts. Interestingly, visual & performing arts has one of the highest advantages derived from the use of Green and of OA generally, yet it is the field with the least prevalent use of OA.

There is a huge citation advantage to publishing in Green OA, as has been demonstrated time and again in other serious studies conducted previously. Papers in general science & technology, historical studies, and visual & performing arts all receive, on average, twice as many citations as the overall population of papers. Two fields stand out for a fairly small Green OA citation advantage: clinical medicine (+8% vs. +56% in Other OA) and biomedical research (+10% vs. +23%). The reason may be that other sources of freely downloadable papers, classified here as 'Other OA,' such as BioMed Central, are so large that the reflex of users is to first see what is available there and to shun institutional repositories. Still, 8% and 10% more citations remains a sizeable advantage and it is worthwhile using institutional repositories and immediate Green OA to cut the delays associated with what many consider as weak OA mandates, that is, allowing for papers to be embargoed instead of being made available immediately.

Table II Proportion of OA per field for papers published between 2011 and 2013

Field	Sample	Green OA		Gold OA journals		Other OA		Total OA		OA Growth	
		Found	%	Found	%	Found	%	Found	%	Trend	Index
Agriculture, Fisheries & Forestry	18,719	519	2.8 ± 0.2	3,019	16.1 ± 0.5	5,829	31.1 ± 0.6	8,784	46.9 ± 0.7	■■■■■■■	1.02
Biology	21,348	792	3.7 ± 0.2	3,631	17.0 ± 0.5	8,974	42.0 ± 0.6	12,324	57.7 ± 0.6	■■■■■■■	1.00
Biomedical Research	39,031	832	2.1 ± 0.1	4,840	12.4 ± 0.3	18,777	48.1 ± 0.5	24,062	61.6 ± 0.5	■■■■■■■	0.99
Built Environment & Design	3,246	151	4.7 ± 0.7	115	3.5 ± 0.6	860	26.5 ± 1.4	1,062	32.7 ± 1.5	■■■■■■■	1.05
Chemistry	42,799	752	1.8 ± 0.1	4,082	9.5 ± 0.3	9,931	23.2 ± 0.4	14,375	33.6 ± 0.4	■■■■■■■	1.03
Clinical Medicine	134,640	2,904	2.2 ± 0.1	19,865	14.8 ± 0.2	46,844	34.8 ± 0.2	66,172	49.1 ± 0.3	■■■■■■■	1.08
Communication & Textual Studies	3,891	140	3.6 ± 0.6	339	8.7 ± 0.8	700	18.0 ± 1.2	1,046	26.9 ± 1.3	■■■■■■■	0.94
Earth & Environmental Sciences	16,589	922	5.6 ± 0.3	1,344	8.1 ± 0.4	6,379	38.5 ± 0.7	8,358	50.4 ± 0.7	■■■■■■■	0.98
Economics & Business	13,475	1,529	11.3 ± 0.5	725	5.4 ± 0.4	4,506	33.4 ± 0.8	6,457	47.9 ± 0.8	■■■■■■■	0.96
Enabling & Strategic Technologies	41,591	1,119	2.7 ± 0.1	3,851	9.3 ± 0.3	9,712	23.4 ± 0.4	14,262	34.3 ± 0.4	■■■■■■■	1.10
Engineering	36,025	1,148	3.2 ± 0.2	1,476	4.1 ± 0.2	8,412	23.4 ± 0.4	10,879	30.2 ± 0.4	■■■■■■■	1.03
Gen. Arts, Humanities & Social Sciences*	6,012	212	3.5	158	2.6	1,651	27.5	1,882	31.3	■■■■■■■	0.85
Gen. Science & Technology	13,663	530	3.9 ± 0.3	7,922	58.0 ± 0.8	2,876	21.0 ± 0.6	10,692	78.3 ± 0.7	■■■■■■■	1.35
Historical Studies	3,491	88	2.5 ± 0.5	251	7.2 ± 0.8	819	23.5 ± 1.3	1,049	30.0 ± 1.4	■■■■■■■	0.98
Information & Communication Tech.	17,781	1,550	8.7 ± 0.4	2,205	12.4 ± 0.5	5,051	28.4 ± 0.6	8,373	47.1 ± 0.7	■■■■■■■	0.97
Mathematics & Statistics	14,288	3,476	24.3 ± 0.7	1,629	11.4 ± 0.5	3,590	25.1 ± 0.7	8,421	58.9 ± 0.8	■■■■■■■	0.90
Philosophy & Theology	2,517	129	5.1 ± 0.8	129	5.1 ± 0.8	563	22.4 ± 1.6	763	30.3 ± 1.7	■■■■■■■	1.00
Physics & Astronomy	46,351	11,862	25.6 ± 0.4	2,382	5.1 ± 0.2	10,369	22.4 ± 0.4	24,012	51.8 ± 0.4	■■■■■■■	1.03
Psychology & Cognitive Sciences	9,849	358	3.6 ± 0.4	548	5.6 ± 0.4	4,194	42.6 ± 0.9	4,961	50.4 ± 0.9	■■■■■■■	0.97
Public Health & Health Services	15,758	476	3.0 ± 0.3	2,485	15.8 ± 0.5	5,168	32.8 ± 0.7	7,864	49.9 ± 0.7	■■■■■■■	1.10
Social Sciences	17,439	898	5.1 ± 0.3	1,510	8.7 ± 0.4	4,740	27.2 ± 0.6	6,638	38.1 ± 0.7	■■■■■■■	1.01
Visual & Performing Arts*	5,162	151	2.9	145	2.8	988	19.1	1,204	23.3	■■■■■■■	1.10
Total**	513,753	30,212	5.9 ± 0.1	62,386	12.1 ± 0.1	158,573	30.9 ± 0.1	240,885	46.9 ± 0.1	■■■■■■■	1.04

Notes: * In General Arts, Humanities & Social Sciences, and Visual & Performing Arts, the whole populations of papers were used instead of a sample.

** The total is computed on the sample only rather than on the sample for all fields and the populations for General Arts, Humanities & Social Sciences, and Visual & Performing Arts.

The growth index was computed using a non-weighted average of 2011 and 2012 over 2008 and 2009. The year 2013 was not used in growth calculation because embargoed OA publications highly affect the score for that year and would give a false sense that OA growth is slowing.

Source: Computed by Science-Metrix using Scopus as well as DOAJ, ROAR, *OpenDOAR*, PubMedCentral and numerous sources of freely downloadable papers.

Table III Number of OA papers published between 2011 and 2013 per field

Field	Sample	Papers in Scopus	Green OA		Gold OA		Other OA		Total OA		Adjusted OA		OA Growth	
			Papers	%	Papers	%	Papers	%	Papers	%	Papers	%	Trend	Index
Agriculture, Fisheries & Forestry	18,719	166,355	4,614	2.8	26,845	16.1	51,807	31.1	78,078	46.9	89,495	53.8		1.16
Biology	21,348	190,080	7,064	3.7	32,321	17.0	79,916	42.0	109,741	57.7	125,788	66.2		1.12
Biomedical Research	39,031	349,681	7,447	2.1	43,364	12.4	167,905	48.0	215,250	61.6	246,725	70.6		1.09
Built Environment & Design	3,246	29,951	1,391	4.6	1,062	3.5	7,933	26	9,796	33	11,228	37.5		1.33
Chemistry	42,799	385,577	6,756	1.8	36,728	9.5	89,396	23.2	129,373	33.6	148,291	38.5		1.18
Clinical Medicine	134,640	1,207,148	26,026	2.2	178,081	14.8	419,871	34.8	593,128	49.1	679,859	56.3		1.19
Communication & Textual Studies	3,891	35,547	1,283	3.6	3,101	8.7	6,405	18	9,573	27	10,973	30.9		1.27
Earth & Environmental Sciences	16,589	149,500	8,315	5.6	12,121	8.1	57,495	38.5	75,342	50.4	86,359	57.8		1.08
Economics & Business	13,475	120,997	13,714	11.3	6,504	5.4	40,432	33.4	57,930	47.9	66,401	54.9		1.16
Enabling & Strategic Technologies	41,591	375,514	10,114	2.7	34,780	9.3	87,681	23.3	128,778	34.3	147,609	39.3		1.34
Engineering	36,025	324,981	10,356	3.2	13,326	4.1	75,885	23.4	98,149	30.2	112,501	34.6		1.20
Gen. Arts, Humanities & Social Sciences*	6,012	6,012	212	3.5	158	2.6	1,651	27.5	1,882	31.3	2,157	35.9		1.04
Gen. Science & Technology	13,663	122,938	4,767	3.9	71,291	58.0	25,874	21.0	96,215	78.3	110,284	89.7		2.43
Historical Studies	3,491	31,256	791	2.5	2,243	7.2	7,330	23	9,389	30	10,762	34.4		1.18
Information & Communication Tech.	17,781	159,873	13,933	8.7	19,856	12.4	45,378	28.4	75,268	47.1	86,275	54.0		1.10
Mathematics & Statistics	14,288	128,423	31,240	24.3	14,613	11.4	32,306	25.2	75,695	58.9	86,764	67.6		1.04
Philosophy & Theology	2,517	22,297	1,140	5.1	1,146	5.1	4,989	22	6,756	30	7,744	34.7		1.24
Physics & Astronomy	46,351	420,062	107,491	25.6	21,582	5.1	93,959	22.4	217,586	51.8	249,403	59.4		1.09
Psychology & Cognitive Sciences	9,849	89,681	3,263	3.6	4,988	5.6	38,195	42.6	45,181	50.4	51,787	57.7		1.10
Public Health & Health Services	15,758	142,459	4,296	3.0	22,462	15.8	46,668	32.8	71,034	49.9	81,421	57.2		1.26
Social Sciences	17,439	156,900	8,085	5.2	13,601	8.7	42,668	27.2	59,763	38.1	68,502	43.7		1.28
Visual & Performing Arts*	5,162	5,162	151	2.9	145	2.8	988	19.1	1,204	23.3	1,380	26.7		1.42
Total**	513,753	4,620,394	271,673	5.9	561,063	12.1	1,425,851	30.9	2,166,106	46.9	2,482,848	53.7		1.19

Notes: * In General Arts, Humanities & Social Sciences, and Visual & Performing Arts, the whole populations of papers were used instead of a sample.
 ** The total is computed on the sample only rather than on the sample for all fields and the populations for General Arts, Humanities & Social Sciences, and Visual & Performing Arts.
 The growth index was computed using a non-weighted average of 2011 and 2012 over 2008 and 2009. The year 2013 was not used in growth calculation because embargoed OA publications highly affect the score for that year and would give a false sense that OA growth is slowing.

Source: Computed by Science-Metrix using Scopus as well as DOAJ, ROAR, *OpenDOAR*, PubMedCentral and numerous sources of freely downloadable papers.

Table IV Rebased scientific impact (ARC) of OA publications, 2009–2011

Field	All types		Green OA		Gold OA		Other OA		Total OA		Not OA	
	Sample	ARC	Found	ARC	Found	ARC	Found	ARC	Found	ARC	Found	ARC
Agriculture, Fisheries & Forestry	18,822	1.00	580	1.57	3,123	0.51	6,009	1.32	9,036	1.13	9,786	0.88
Biology	22,160	1.00	912	1.30	3,658	0.47	9,837	1.37	13,317	1.21	8,843	0.69
Biomedical Research	40,225	1.00	949	1.10	4,618	0.91	21,385	1.23	26,495	1.18	13,730	0.65
Built Environment & Design	3,102	1.00	169	1.56	108	0.19	803	1.28	1,009	1.29	2,093	0.86
Chemistry	42,457	1.00	897	1.28	4,152	0.34	10,354	1.34	15,022	1.09	27,435	0.95
Clinical Medicine	138,945	1.00	3,216	1.08	16,747	0.64	52,253	1.56	69,119	1.37	69,826	0.63
Communication & Textual Studies	4,156	1.00	169	1.51	242	0.66	879	1.82	1,188	1.66	2,968	0.73
Earth & Environmental Sciences	16,365	1.00	1,059	1.46	1,201	0.98	6,594	1.26	8,540	1.26	7,825	0.72
Economics & Business	13,518	1.00	1,638	1.46	712	0.22	4,918	1.30	6,988	1.28	6,530	0.71
Enabling & Strategic Technologies	39,694	1.00	1,277	1.68	3,445	0.52	9,270	1.53	13,550	1.33	26,144	0.83
Engineering	35,285	1.00	1,311	1.84	927	0.55	8,681	1.38	10,788	1.38	24,497	0.83
General Arts, Humanities & Social Sciences	6,772	1.00	268	1.74	116	0.13	2,068	1.49	2,354	1.51	4,418	0.73
General Science & Technology	9,594	1.00	405	2.56	3,710	0.69	2,633	2.24	6,157	1.50	3,437	0.11
Historical Studies	3,840	1.00	144	2.37	264	0.37	885	1.61	1,173	1.55	2,667	0.76
Information & Communication Technology	17,167	1.00	1,667	1.62	1,482	0.76	5,517	1.36	8,345	1.33	8,822	0.69
Mathematics & Statistics	13,750	1.00	3,147	1.35	1,073	0.67	4,547	1.11	8,518	1.15	5,232	0.75
Philosophy & Theology	2,532	1.00	108	1.72	144	0.86	595	1.63	783	1.63	1,749	0.72
Physics & Astronomy	46,239	1.00	11,864	1.43	2,177	1.18	11,158	1.04	24,658	1.24	21,581	0.73
Psychology & Cognitive Sciences	9,803	1.00	457	1.31	529	0.59	4,451	1.35	5,284	1.29	4,519	0.66
Public Health & Health Services	15,812	1.00	533	1.30	2,291	0.71	5,575	1.38	8,073	1.23	7,739	0.76
Social Sciences	17,606	1.00	1,020	1.54	1,441	0.52	5,199	1.44	7,136	1.36	10,470	0.76
Visual & Performing Arts	5,724	1.00	167	2.16	185	0.29	1,034	1.86	1,280	1.80	4,444	0.77
Total	512,443	1.00	31,561	1.53	52,080	0.61	171,885	1.36	245,571	1.26	266,872	0.76

Note: Colour-coding indicates performances above the world level in a given field (Green) or below the world level in the same field (red).

Source: Computed by Science-Metrix using Scopus as well as DOAJ, ROAR, OpenDOAR, PubMedCentral and numerous sources of freely downloadable papers.

Table V presents the same data as Table IV except this time it shows, all things being equal, how rational scientists would behave if they wanted to maximise their chance of having a great scientific impact. Clearly, in order to increase the chance of being highly cited, self-archiving in Green OA is the best option, as it comes in first 15 times and second 7 times. Considering that self-archiving is free, rationale scientists would consider this choice the most obvious choice. Other forms of OA, which is not a homogeneous category and varies by field, would appear to be the second best choice. The third place would go to publishing in a subscription journal and leaving it as it is. For 22 fields, papers that are not available in OA never make it to the top position in terms of impact, on average, and do not even make second place. In fact, in the case of seven fields, this would be the least rational choice for a scientist who wants to make a difference and be cited as much as possible. Gold OA makes it to second place once and to third six times, but loses out in 15 fields. Giving a full point for first place, 2/3 for second, 1/3 for third and no point for having the least impact confirms the general ranking: Green OA, Other OA, Not OA and Gold OA.

Table V Impact contest by OA type by field, 2009–2011

Field	1st place		2nd place		3rd place		Least impact	
	Type	ARC	Type	ARC	Type	ARC	Type	ARC
Agriculture, Fisheries & Forestry	Green OA	1.57	Other OA	1.32	Not OA	0.88	Gold OA	0.51
Biology	Other OA	1.37	Green OA	1.30	Not OA	0.69	Gold OA	0.47
Biomedical Research	Other OA	1.23	Green OA	1.10	Gold OA	0.91	Not OA	0.65
Built Environment & Design	Green OA	1.56	Other OA	1.28	Not OA	0.86	Gold OA	0.19
Chemistry	Other OA	1.34	Green OA	1.28	Not OA	0.95	Gold OA	0.34
Clinical Medicine	Other OA	1.56	Green OA	1.08	Gold OA	0.64	Not OA	0.63
Communication & Textual Studies	Other OA	1.82	Green OA	1.51	Not OA	0.66	Gold OA	0.73
Earth & Environmental Sciences	Green OA	1.46	Other OA	1.26	Gold OA	0.98	Not OA	0.72
Economics & Business	Green OA	1.46	Other OA	1.30	Not OA	0.71	Gold OA	0.22
Enabling & Strategic Technologies	Green OA	1.68	Other OA	1.53	Not OA	0.83	Gold OA	0.52
Engineering	Green OA	1.84	Other OA	1.38	Not OA	0.83	Gold OA	0.55
General Arts, Humanities & Social Sciences	Green OA	1.74	Other OA	1.49	Not OA	0.73	Gold OA	0.13
General Science & Technology	Green OA	2.56	Other OA	2.24	Gold OA	0.69	Not OA	0.11
Historical Studies	Green OA	2.37	Other OA	1.61	Not OA	0.76	Gold OA	0.37
Information & Communication Technology	Green OA	1.62	Other OA	1.36	Gold OA	0.76	Not OA	0.69
Mathematics & Statistics	Green OA	1.35	Other OA	1.11	Not OA	0.75	Gold OA	0.67
Philosophy & Theology	Green OA	1.72	Other OA	1.63	Gold OA	0.86	Not OA	0.72
Physics & Astronomy	Green OA	1.43	Gold OA	1.18	Other OA	1.04	Not OA	0.73
Psychology & Cognitive Sciences	Other OA	1.35	Green OA	1.31	Not OA	0.66	Gold OA	0.59
Public Health & Health Services	Other OA	1.38	Green OA	1.30	Not OA	0.76	Gold OA	0.71
Social Sciences	Green OA	1.54	Other OA	1.44	Not OA	0.76	Gold OA	0.52
Visual & Performing Arts	Green OA	2.16	Other OA	1.86	Not OA	0.77	Gold OA	0.29
Total	Green OA	1.53	Other OA	1.36	Not OA	0.76	Gold OA	0.61

Contest Results

Contestants	Count of 1st place	Points (1)
Green OA	15	15
Other OA	7	7
Contestants	Count of 2nd place	Points (2/3)
Other OA	14	9.3
Green OA	7	4.7
Gold OA	1	0.7
Contestants	Count of 3rd place	Points (1/3)
Not OA	15	5.0
Gold OA	6	2.0
Other OA	1	0.3
Contestants	Count of Least impact	Points (0)
Not OA	7	0
Gold OA	15	0

Contest Total Point Table

Type	Points
Green OA	19.7
Other OA	16.7
Not OA	5.0
Gold OA	2.7

Source: Computed by Science-Metrix using Scopus as well as DOAJ, ROAR, *OpenDOAR*, PubMedCentral and numerous sources of freely downloadable papers.

4.4 OA availability of papers published between 2008 and 2013 in the European Research Area and selected countries

The EU28 and ERA have slightly more than the level of OA observed at the world level (around 58.6% for the 2008–2013 period for the EU and ERA versus 53.9% at the world level, although there are notable differences among countries (Table VI)). For the 2008–2013 period as a whole, all EU28 countries have reached a ‘tipping point.’ Looking at OA score adjusted for retrieval precision and recall, four countries have even reached an aggregate availability score above 70%—the Netherlands, Croatia, Estonia and Portugal. It is interesting to note that the Netherlands, which is also the land of predilection for scientific publishers, is the EU country with the largest share of papers available in OA form (74%) as a whole for papers published in the 2008–2013 period and available for free downloading as of April 2014.

All ERA countries have tipped towards having a majority of papers in OA, though in the case of the Republic of Moldova the margin of error is quite high and it is quite possible that the country has not tipped to OA yet. Swiss researchers contribute to making their country a leader in OA with 70% of the papers being downloadable for free.

Table VI Proportion of OA per country, 2008–2013

Group	Country	Sample size	Green OA		Gold OA journals		Other OA		Total OA		Adjusted OA
			Found	%	Found	%	Found	%	Found	%	%
	Austria	8,764	821	9.4 ± 0.6	775	8.8 ± 0.6	3,450	39.4 ± 1.0	4,855	55.4 ± 1.0	63.5 ± 4.6
	Belgium	13,147	1,813	13.8 ± 0.6	968	7.4 ± 0.4	5,210	39.6 ± 0.8	7,841	59.6 ± 0.8	68.4 ± 4.6
	Bulgaria	1,707	161	9.4 ± 1.3	126	7.4 ± 1.2	558	33 ± 2	829	49 ± 2	56 ± 5
	Croatia	2,954	153	5.2 ± 0.8	687	23 ± 1.5	1,149	38.9 ± 1.7	1,876	63.5 ± 1.7	72.8 ± 4.8
	Cyprus	584	72	12 ± 3	43	7 ± 2	223	38 ± 4	329	56 ± 4	65 ± 6
	Czech Republic	7,637	521	6.8 ± 0.5	736	9.6 ± 0.6	2,598	34.0 ± 1.0	3,718	48.7 ± 1.1	55.8 ± 4.6
	Denmark	9,097	871	9.6 ± 0.6	819	9.0 ± 0.6	3,539	38.9 ± 1.0	5,127	56.4 ± 1.0	64.6 ± 4.6
	Estonia	932	81	8.7 ± 1.8	123	13 ± 2	390	42 ± 3	577	62 ± 3	71 ± 5
	Finland	7,414	659	8.9 ± 0.6	690	9.3 ± 0.6	2,838	38.3 ± 1.0	4,102	55.3 ± 1.1	63.4 ± 4.6
	France	48,991	6,881	14.0 ± 0.3	3,255	6.6 ± 0.2	16,560	33.8 ± 0.4	25,915	52.9 ± 0.4	60.6 ± 4.5
	Germany	66,268	7,575	11.4 ± 0.2	5,065	7.6 ± 0.2	21,993	33.2 ± 0.3	33,735	50.9 ± 0.4	58.4 ± 4.5
	Greece	8,043	525	6.5 ± 0.5	773	9.6 ± 0.6	3,067	38.1 ± 1.0	4,246	52.8 ± 1.0	60.5 ± 4.6
	Hungary	4,559	454	10.0 ± 0.8	356	7.8 ± 0.7	2,023	44 ± 1.4	2,782	61.0 ± 1.3	69.9 ± 4.7
	Ireland	5,150	815	15.8 ± 0.9	472	9.2 ± 0.8	1,839	36 ± 1.2	3,018	58.6 ± 1.3	67.2 ± 4.7
EU28	Italy	39,117	3,691	9.4 ± 0.3	3,112	8.0 ± 0.3	14,594	37.3 ± 0.5	21,021	53.7 ± 0.5	61.6 ± 4.5
&	Latvia	387	21	5.4 ± 2.3	57	15 ± 3	156	40 ± 5	232	60 ± 5	69 ± 7
ERA	Lithuania	1,434	65	4.5 ± 1.0	183	12.8 ± 1.7	593	41 ± 2	811	57 ± 2	65 ± 5
	Luxembourg	417	46	11.0 ± 3.0	36	9 ± 3	174	42 ± 5	253	61 ± 5	70 ± 6
	Malta	140	7	5.0 ± 3.8	30	21 ± 7	41	29 ± 7	75	54 ± 8	61 ± 9
	Netherlands	23,564	2,863	12.1 ± 0.4	1,883	8.0 ± 0.3	10,707	45.4 ± 0.6	15,177	64.4 ± 0.6	73.8 ± 4.5
	Poland	15,628	1,112	7.1 ± 0.4	2,099	13.4 ± 0.5	4,695	30.0 ± 0.7	7,416	47.5 ± 0.7	54.4 ± 4.5
	Portugal	7,190	1,169	16.3 ± 0.8	747	10.4 ± 0.7	2,636	36.7 ± 1.1	4,422	61.5 ± 1.1	70.5 ± 4.6
	Romania	5,105	271	5.3 ± 0.6	487	9.5 ± 0.8	1,994	39.1 ± 1.3	2,647	51.9 ± 1.3	59.4 ± 4.7
	Slovakia	2,372	156	6.6 ± 1.0	240	10.1 ± 1.2	798	33.6 ± 1.8	1,155	48.7 ± 1.9	55.8 ± 4.9
	Slovenia	2,586	181	7.0 ± 0.9	425	16.4 ± 1.4	871	33.7 ± 1.7	1,369	52.9 ± 1.8	60.7 ± 4.8
	Spain	35,557	3,517	9.9 ± 0.3	4,074	11.5 ± 0.3	12,119	34.1 ± 0.5	18,341	51.6 ± 0.5	59.1 ± 4.5
	Sweden	14,872	1,527	10.3 ± 0.5	1,460	9.8 ± 0.5	5,767	38.8 ± 0.7	8,587	57.7 ± 0.8	66.2 ± 4.5
	United Kingdom	73,621	8,506	11.6 ± 0.2	5,265	7.2 ± 0.2	28,173	38.3 ± 0.3	41,133	55.9 ± 0.3	64.0 ± 4.5
Total EU28		337,231	31,635	9.4 ± 0.1	29,165	8.6 ± 0.1	117,793	34.9 ± 0.2	172,956	51.3 ± 0.2	58.8 ± 4.5
	Albania	87	4	5 ± 5	16	18 ± 8	25	29 ± 10	43	49 ± 11	57 ± 11
	Bosnia and Herzegovina	362	3	0.8 ± 1.0	92	25 ± 4	139	38 ± 5	226	62 ± 5	72 ± 7
	Iceland	554	57	10.3 ± 2.5	37	7 ± 2	269	49 ± 4	354	64 ± 4	73 ± 6
	Israel	8,450	894	10.6 ± 0.6	502	5.9 ± 0.5	3,552	42.0 ± 1.0	4,882	57.8 ± 1.0	66.2 ± 4.6
ERA	Liechtenstein	40	5	13 ± 11			20	50 ± 16	25	63 ± 15	72 ± 16
Associated	FYR Macedonia	255	18	7 ± 3	75	29 ± 5	87	34 ± 6	173	68 ± 6	78 ± 7
Countries	Montenegro	104	6	6 ± 5	30	29 ± 9	38	37 ± 9	71	68 ± 9	78 ± 10
	Norway	7,280	629	8.6 ± 0.6	705	9.7 ± 0.6	2,907	39.9 ± 1.1	4,145	56.9 ± 1.1	65.3 ± 4.6
	Rep. of Moldova	160	14	9 ± 4	5	3 ± 3	52	33 ± 7	71	44 ± 8	51 ± 9
	Serbia	2,997	135	4.5 ± 0.7	906	30.2 ± 1.6	803	26.8 ± 1.5	1,786	59.6 ± 1.7	68.3 ± 4.8
	Switzerland	16,896	2,497	14.8 ± 0.5	1,547	9.2 ± 0.4	6,630	39.2 ± 0.7	10,369	61.4 ± 0.7	70.3 ± 4.5
	Turkey	17,420	475	2.7 ± 0.2	3,458	19.9 ± 0.6	4,853	27.9 ± 0.6	7,962	45.7 ± 0.7	52.4 ± 4.5
Total ERA		375,820	33,766	9.0 ± 0.1	34,932	9.3 ± 0.1	130,244	34.7 ± 0.1	192,202	51.1 ± 0.2	58.6 ± 4.5
Others	Brazil	26,158	1,626	6.2 ± 0.3	10,482	40.1 ± 0.6	6,515	24.9 ± 0.5	17,322	66.2 ± 0.5	75.9 ± 4.5
	Canada	41,114	2,895	7.0 ± 0.2	3,098	7.5 ± 0.2	17,438	42.4 ± 0.5	23,096	56.2 ± 0.5	64.4 ± 4.5
	Japan	58,527	4,170	7.1 ± 0.2	5,382	9.2 ± 0.2	16,883	28.8 ± 0.3	25,846	44.2 ± 0.4	50.6 ± 4.5
	United States	258,815	17,865	6.9 ± 0.1	17,709	6.8 ± 0.1	119,943	46.3 ± 0.2	153,416	59.3 ± 0.2	67.9 ± 4.5
World		1,000,000	60,271	6.0 ± 0.04	104,050	10.4 ± 0.1	324,637	32.5 ± 0.1	470,530	47.1 ± 0.1	53.9 ± 4.5

Source: Computed by Science-Metrix using DOAJ, PubMedCentral and Scopus.

In countries outside the ERA, it is noteworthy that the US has passed the tipping point by a fair margin (adjusted OA=67.9%), as is also the case for Canada (64.4%). Even more salient is the

proportion of 76% observed in Brazil. This is no doubt due to the important contribution of SciELO, which plays a key role in the Southern hemisphere in making scientific knowledge more widely available. Japan is just a hair over 50% and, given the margin of error of adjusted OA, may or may not have tipped to having a majority of papers in OA form.

Within the European Union, Green OA is more widely used in Portugal (16.3%), Ireland (15.8%), France (14.0%) and Belgium (13.8%), and least used in Lithuania (4.5%), Malta (5.0%), Croatia (5.2%) and Romania (5.3%).

Publishing in Gold journals is much more frequently encountered in Eastern Europe, as it is much higher in Croatia, Slovenia, Latvia, Poland, Estonia and Lithuania (in addition to Malta). One interesting hypothesis is that researchers in these countries may use Gold journals because they more frequently allow publishing in languages other than English. Should that be the case, this may also contribute to explaining the lower citation scores received by papers in Gold journals as the readership for ‘vernacular languages,’ to quote Eugene Garfield (1998), is lower and the potential reference pool is consequently also smaller. There is therefore potentially fertile ground for studying the social and linguistic aspects of science by examining where and why Gold OA journals are appearing and who actually makes use of them. The countries that use the least Gold OA journals are France (6.6%), the UK (7.2%) and Belgium (7.4%).

The large sample of publications used for this final version of the study ($n=1,000,000$) makes it possible to produce more disaggregated data. The Appendix presents data across the selected countries at the field level for Green, Gold, Other OA and Total OA availability (not adjusted for the harvesting instrument’s limits, so these are floor values).

4.5 Composite indicator of open access growth

This section presents findings pertaining to the growth of open access obtained through the computation of a composite indicator of open access growth (CIOAG). Section 4.5.1 details the construction of the CIOAG while Section 4.5.2 presents the key findings based on this measure.

4.5.1 Approach to the computation of the CIOAG

The following steps were carried out in building the composite measure (inspired from OECD, 2008): development of the measurement framework for quantifying the growth of OA (including the selection of the variables to be included), normalisation and standardisation of the indicators, weighting of the indicator, aggregation of the indicators in a composite measure, and robustness and sensitivity analysis of the composite indicator.

The growth of the following variables was examined for inclusion in the composite indicator: annual proportion of a country’s papers published in Gold OA journals, annual number of Gold OA journals, annual proportion of a country’s papers published in Green OA (i.e. self-archived versions of papers [in OA repositories] published in subscription-based journals), annual proportion of a country’s papers classified in other OA (i.e., heterogeneous mix of papers including, but not limited to, papers made available for free by editors, or because authors paid fees to provide free access to their papers), annual number of open access repositories, and annual number of open access policies adopted.

From a theoretical standpoint, the existence of OA policies is critical to the development of OA as a means of dissemination of research outputs. Unfortunately, the growth of policies could not be reliably computed for enough countries and was therefore set aside in the computation of the CIOAG. Data on the annual number of repositories also had to be left out.

In computing the CIOAG, the growth of individual indicator was measured as the simple ratio between the average score in 2011–2013 over 2008–2010:

$$\text{Growth} = \text{Score}_{2011-2013} / \text{Score}_{2008-2010}$$

All growth measures were found to approximately follow a Gaussian distribution such that no transformation was required prior to standardization. A similarity-based approach to the positive ideal solution (i.e. the maximum score across all indicators based on the selection of countries) was used in aggregating the selected indicators of OA growth. To measure the similarity between a country's performance and the positive ideal solution, the scores for each indicator were standardised by the maximum for the corresponding indicator so that they subsequently ranged between 0 (worst possible performance) and 1 (maximum observed growth).

The relative influence of each of the retained indicators (i.e. growth in the share of papers in Gold OA journals, in Green OA, in Other OA and in the number of Gold OA journals) on the resulting CIOAG was balanced through the application of a differential weighting such that each of them explained approximately the same amount of the variation in the CIOAG (roughly 15% each).

4.5.2 Key findings

Note that the CIOAG could not be computed for 7 out of 39 countries where growth data were missing for one or more of the indicators used. As with any composite indicator, careful interpretation of the results is essential to avoid simplistic conclusions. Composite indicators must be seen as a means of initiating discussion and stimulating interest (OECD, 2008).

The results show that Eastern European countries³² are among those experiencing the strongest OA growth with six of them ranking in the top ten (Slovakia in 1st place, Poland in 2nd, Hungary in 4th, Bulgaria in 6th, Czech Republic in 7th and Romania in 8th). There is a moderate negative correlation between the share of papers in Gold OA journals and the share of Green/Other OA publications. However, there does not seem to be any correlation between these shares and the CIOAG. Thus, countries that exhibit strong performance in the growth of the proportion of their output that is available in OA do not *de facto* exhibit strong or weak performance in terms of the actual share of their output which is available for free.

For example, Brazil appears in 21st place based on the composite measure of growth despite having the 2nd largest number of Gold OA journals as of 2013 as well as the largest share of publications in Gold OA journals relative to its total publication output. On the other hand, Switzerland which ranks 5th based on the CIOAG also ranks high (2nd) for the share of its output available in Green/Other OA. Besides Switzerland, other traditional leaders in scientific performance that rank high in terms of OA growth include Sweden (3rd), Italy (8th), Germany (9th) and Austria (10th).

³² As defined by the United Nations Statistics Division, <https://unstats.un.org/unsd/methods/m49/m49reqin.htm>

5 Discussion and policy implications

The main study's findings as relates to the development of OA strategies for the open access to scientific publications and scientific data as well as to the growth of the share of scholarly publications which is available in OA are summarised below along with a discussion of policy implications.

OA to scientific publications

It has been suggested that OA to scientific papers improves the speed, efficiency and efficacy of research by allowing researchers faster access to the information they need. For authors, it can shorten the delay between acceptance and publication in a journal. It also increases the visibility and usage of their research and results in greater research impact due to increased citations. What is particularly interesting here is that the citation advantage is derived almost exclusively from the Green and Other OA portion, as Paid Access (not OA) is systematically ranking behind Green OA and Other OA and is the option yielding the lowest scientific impact (smaller number of citations received by papers on average) for seven fields. The model may help to relieve the 'serials crisis' and save the direct costs of print publication and dissemination.

The main bottlenecks that have prevented OA from gaining greater acceptance among stakeholders include a lack of awareness among researchers, concerns about the quality and prestige of OA journals, concerns and confusion regarding copyright, the dissuasive influence of author-side fees, difficulties moving beyond the current system of subscription-based journals, the lack of useful data on OA's evolution, a perceived lack of profitability surrounding OA business models and a lack of infrastructure to support OA in developing countries. Despite these barriers, this investigation concludes that OA has become the dominant form of dissemination of peer-reviewed scholarly articles in the ERA, Brazil, Canada, Japan and the US.

OA to scientific data

Open data is evolving rapidly in an environment where citizens, institutions, governments, non-profits and private corporations loosely cooperate to develop infrastructure, standards, prototypes and business models. From a government perspective, open data confers a competitive advantage in an increasingly information-based economy. New products and services can be developed directly from the data or through extensive transformation that adds value to the information. Additionally, the legal and economic implications for publishers are far fewer for open data than for open access to scholarly publications. In fact, the Association of Learned and Professional Society Publishers (ALPSP) and the International Association of Scientific, Technical & Medical Publishers (STM) have declared their support of OA scientific data initiatives.

The emergence of OA scientific data as a valid, citable form of reference is limited by the difficulties associated with the standardisation of data and metadata formats, poor indexation by internet browsers and the scarcity of directories or registries that could make data more visible.

Increasingly, disciplinary standards are being developed to index specific types of records in the face of an ever-rising tide of data. However, the heterogeneous nature of scientific data is a challenge for the development of OA in this area. A few fields of research use highly standardised formats that facilitate the aggregation and re-use of data, with genomics, proteomics, chemical crystallography, geography, astronomy and archaeology among them. The archiving of other, less standardised types of data needs to be carefully considered in order to generate datasets that will be usable by other researchers.

Whereas researchers have a ‘natural incentive’ to promote OA in the case of scholarly publications, as this makes their work more widely known, in some cases there might be negative incentives to make research data public. Researchers may indeed derive a competitive advantage by filling up their own data warehouse, and widely diffusing these data may limit the growth and curtail the size of their research enterprises.

Strengths and weaknesses of strategies promoting OA to scientific publications and data

The prevalence and success of the approaches used vary widely across the examined countries and depending on the type of approaches used, which can be grouped as the following:

- National legislation addressing OA;
- National projects, programmes and initiatives promoting OA;
- Funders’ mandates requiring Green self-archiving in OA repositories;
- Institutions’ mandates requiring Green self-archiving in OA repositories;
- Funders’ or institutions’ policies and mandates to publish in OA journals; and
- Development of OA infrastructure.

National legislation addressing OA

Main strengths: Theoretically, national legislation mandating OA has the greatest potential to influence the adoption of OA in a country and make OA the ‘default’ in that country’s scholarly communication system. OA laws would help to ensure that taxpayers have access to the results of the research that they collectively fund.

Main weaknesses: Legal directives on OA can be difficult to formulate due to their inherent complexity and potentially significant implications for many stakeholder groups. Proposed laws on OA can sometimes generate controversy and face pushback from powerful bodies that hinder implementation (stakeholders may, for example, perceive a strong government mandate as dictating where researchers must publish outputs, raising fundamental issues of academic freedom).

National projects, programmes and initiatives promoting OA

Main strengths: National initiatives provide a good opportunity to address the concerns and correct the misconceptions that many have about OA and to raise awareness of OA. They can potentially bring together a range of stakeholders in the debate on scientific information.

Main weaknesses: While the vast majority of initiatives are led by policy makers or institutional libraries and library associations, comparatively few researchers are participating in the debate.

Funders’ mandates requiring Green self-archiving in open access repositories

Main strengths: Mandates issued by funders vastly improve awareness of OA among researchers and compliance with a self-archiving policy. While about 15% of articles are spontaneously self-archived, institutions with mandates can achieve far higher compliance.³³ Increased compliance allows funders to better monitor the outcomes of their investments and

³³ Harnad, S., et al. (2009). Maximizing and measuring research impact through university and research-funder open-access self-archiving mandates. *Wissenschaftsmanagement*, 15(4), 36–41. <http://eprints.soton.ac.uk/266616/>

raises the visibility and impact of the funded research. Greater levels of self-archiving also help to ensure the long-term preservation and accessibility of the research and scientific data.

Main weaknesses: Most policy statements encourage, rather than mandate, the use of Green or Gold OA. Few funding bodies track compliance rates with OA policies. Inequalities exist in the level of detail provided in funder policies, and many funders' policies omit important information for users. Mandates requiring the use only of journals that comply with policies can cut off potential publishing avenues for researchers, raising concerns about academic freedom.

Institutions' mandates requiring Green self-archiving in open access repositories

Main strengths: Mandates issued by institutions vastly improve awareness of OA among researchers and compliance with a self-archiving policy. They are better able to form a complete record of and showcase their intellectual effort and output, as well as to share, measure and analyse their research output, and subsequently manage research programmes. Researchers maximise the visibility and impact of their research. OA to scientific data has the potential to strengthen the credibility of scholarly publications and research institutions, as it opens peer review to the entire scientific community.

Main weaknesses: There are many more repositories than there are mandates requiring their use. Institutions may hesitate to enact OA mandates out of reluctance to raise the administrative burden of researchers and staff. Institutions rarely monitor compliance with OA policies. Institutional repositories often have poor interoperability with other repositories. Most repositories guarantee only medium-term availability of their collections. The academic community continues to have persistent reservations about OA with respect to copyright issues, quality control, the authenticity of OA documents and the time and effort needed to deposit works. OA to scientific data lacks the championing efforts made for OA to scientific publications.

Funders' or institutions' policies and mandates to publish in OA journals

Main strengths: Researchers who publish in OA journals potentially have enhanced visibility, wider dissemination and greater usage. Mandates increase compliance of researchers and publishing rates in Gold OA journals, increasing the credibility of OA peer-reviewed publications. Research funders have access to the outputs they have funded, allowing them to monitor these outputs and adjust programming accordingly. Indirect costs of publishing in OA journals are increasingly being subsidised by funding bodies or administered at the faculty/department level of institutions.

Main weaknesses: The publication-fee Gold OA model is hampered by the dissuasive influence of author-side fees. Researchers may also resist publishing in OA journals due to lack of knowledge about relevant copyright issues or concerns about the quality, prestige or impact of OA journals. The impact of Gold OA journals remains low on average in several fields.

Development of open access infrastructure

Main strengths: Progress has been made in all aspects related to improving repository interoperability. Several free software packages are available for the creation and management of institutional repositories. Such technological developments ensure that the marginal costs of providing online access to documents are fairly low.

Main weaknesses: Although many European national repository infrastructures have been created, they are not yet sufficiently interconnected or searchable by machines (crawlers), isolating repository contents from readers and harvesters. Technical challenges facing

repositories include the non-uniformity of manuscript files and metadata formats, embargo management and author authentication for repository deposit, and the long-term availability of collections. The costs of setting up and maintaining repositories can be prohibitive, in some cases. There are relatively few institutional repositories dedicated to research data.

Analysis of trends in the proportion and number of papers available in OA

If one makes a straight reading of the data presented in this report, between 2008 and 2013, the average annual rate of increase of OA availability was relatively limited. Importantly though, the study shows that examining the growth of OA based solely on a snapshot of OA availability at a given time tells only a small part of the story. There are four types of growth in freely available papers: (1) historical growth in the interest in OA, which translates into *new papers* being increasingly available for free; (2) the growing interest in OA, which translates into actors increasingly making available *old papers* for free; (3) OA policies that allow for delaying OA to scientific papers with embargo periods, which produce a concomitant disembargoing of scientific articles that creates additional growth in old papers being made available for free; and (4) the fact that the number of papers is growing, which means that even for a stable proportion of OA, the number of OA papers would keep growing.

The percentage of peer-reviewed articles published in Gold OA journals indexed in Scopus increased from 1996 to 2012, the annual growth rate being 18% for this period, meaning that the proportion of articles in Gold OA journals doubles every 4.1 years. The number of Gold OA papers indexed in Scopus up until 2012 also grew exponentially. The growth rate was 24% per year between 1996 and 2012, which means that the number of papers published in Gold OA journals doubles every 3.2 years. Although the growth of papers is particularly clear for those in Gold OA journals, papers in Green OA form and in Other OA have also been available in increasingly large numbers during the 18-year period covered by this study.

An estimate of the backfilling of old papers published between 1996 and 2011 and made available for free during the year separating the measures made in April 2013 (previous version of this study) and in April 2014 (the present update) reveals that backfilling is truly important for understanding how OA grows: a total of 700,000 papers published between 1996 and 2011, as indexed in Scopus, were made available for free between April 2013 and April 2014. Considering that there are about 18 million papers in Scopus for that period, this represents an increase in availability of 3.9 percentage points in just one year. This provides evidence that the growth in the number of papers through backfilling is of the same order of magnitude as the growth in newly published papers being made available every year.

When one looks at the availability curve, it can be seen that availability fell somewhat in more recent years. This is due to the presence of embargos for some of the subscription-based journals, which make all articles freely available to all after a few years—the form of open access called DOA (Delayed OA). DOA is a multi-faceted phenomenon. The translation in the availability curve is itself a manifestation of DOA. This occurs when researchers decide to make their own papers available for free and self-archive them in institutional repositories or in Robin Hood OA (ROA), that is, when they decide to make papers available in whatever form they were finally published regardless of the rules that publishers have stated and that are compiled on the University of Nottingham's SHERPA/RoMEO list. It also occurs when subscription-based journals ('Paid Access' or PA) convert to Gold journals and provide back issues for free. Also, and importantly, several OA mandates—the types of mandates which OA advocates frequently consider to be half-baked measures—allow research results to be available in the form of DOA.

There are also transient effects that have to be considered when measuring OA availability; papers that come and go can be called TOA (Transient OA). Many articles that were available for free in December 2012 were no longer available for free in April 2013, and some articles that were available last year disappeared during the year, showing that TOA is an important phenomenon to contend with. This is in part due to a promotion Springer was running in late 2012 by making several subscription-journal papers available for free, and later making them available for a fee again. Some articles disappeared from websites, and some websites were not responding when visited, thus reducing further OA availability. This shows that measuring phenomena on the Internet requires particular attention to detail and constant questioning on the meaning of the results—one has to ask whether these results are permanent or transient.

The main bottlenecks that have prevented OA from gaining greater acceptance among stakeholders include a lack of awareness among researchers, concerns about the quality and prestige of OA journals, concerns and confusion about copyright, the dissuasive influence of article processing charges, difficulties moving beyond the current system of subscription-based journals, the lack of useful data on OA's evolution, a perceived lack of profitability surrounding OA business models, and a lack of infrastructure to support OA in developing countries.

Despite the presence of these barriers, this investigation concludes that OA has become the dominant form of dissemination of peer-reviewed scholarly articles in the ERA, Brazil, Canada, Japan, and US. Though only a few years ago research suggested that OA growth was modest, a series of studies conducted by Science-Metrix for the European Commission provides undeniable evidence that the OA movement is disruptive and that OA is traversing the scientific, technical and medical publishing industry with the speed and force of a tsunami.

Much has been said about the cost of publishing in Gold OA journals and for Gold OA articles ('hybrid publishing'). The cost of academic papers in the US is over \$100,000—which is calculated by dividing the higher education expenditures on R&D (HERD) by the number of papers published by academia. In addition to or included in this amount, a \$2,000 OA publication fee only accounts for a few percentage points of a typical research project budget, especially in the natural and health sciences. Green OA is free, and the majority of publishers accept that papers can be self-archived in one form or another (pre-print, post-print with final revision, or PDF) with no delay. Moreover, two-thirds of Gold OA journals do not levy author processing charges (Suber, 2013). There are free avenues to OA and cost should not be construed as a barrier.

It has been suggested that OA to scientific papers improves the speed, efficiency and efficacy of research by allowing researchers faster access to the information they need. It increases the visibility, usage of scientific impact of research. The model may help to relieve the 'serials crisis' and save the direct costs of print publication and dissemination. For authors, it can shorten the delay between acceptance and publication in a journal. What is particularly interesting here is that the citation advantage is derived almost exclusively from the Green and Other OA portion, as Paid Access (not OA) systematically ranks behind Green OA and Other OA, and is an option yielding the lowest scientific impact (smaller number of citations received by papers on average) for seven fields. Publishing in Gold OA journals provides the least impactful choice in 15 out of 22 fields, and this low impact is probably more a reflection of the youth of these journals rather than anything else. Yet Gold OA journals beat Paid Access journals in 7 disciplines, showing that well-established Paid Access journals are losing their predominance and perhaps even their relevance in several fields of science. Despite their youth, Gold OA journals may continue to dislodge them in additional fields as their contents continue to improve. The day that articles that stay solely behind a pay wall will have lost their relevance may be edging closer faster than anyone expects.

The current model of back-end toll access is simply unsustainable because of its gross social inefficiency and ineffectiveness. Examining the OECD statistics on gross domestic expenditure on R&D in OECD and selected 'Non-OECD Member Economies' (Argentina, China, Romania, Russian Federation, Singapore, South Africa, Chinese Taipei),³⁴ and using some conservative extrapolations, one can see that about \$400 billion (current dollars at purchasing dollar parity) were spent by governments (GovERD) to support R&D. The revenues generated by science, technical and medical publishing (STM) for English-speaking countries was worth approximately \$9.4 billion in the same year (Ware & Mabe, 2012). Though these figures are not immediately comparable as part of the industry must derive income from non-English journals, the fact remains that a sizeable part of the research results paid for by \$400 billion in publicly spent money is either delayed, restricted, or still simply behind thick pay walls and generates only \$10 billion in private wealth. This is a case of gross inefficiency, one that taxpayers the world over should not tolerate.

Just as there is a need for policy-makers, researchers, research administrators, and the tax-paying public to consider the inefficiency created by all this public expenditure being made unavailable or available with undue restrictions, difficulties and delays, there is a need to closely monitor the effects of moving the scientific world from one based on Back End Paid Access (BEPA) to one based on Front End Paid Access (FEPA). BEPA created huge social inefficiency; FEPA has the potential to enlarge the rift between wealthier and more poorly financed countries, researchers and scientific disciplines. Many mandates being promulgated at the moment run the risk of favouring a shift from BEPA to FEPA, from inaccessibility to inequality. Neither inaccessibility nor growing inequality are acceptable considering that universalism is one of the core values of scientific research.

³⁴ https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=GERD_FUNDS

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